

**PREDICTION OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CEMENT
BLENDED FLY ASH-PERIWINKLE SHELL ASH SANDCRETE
BLOCKS**

BY

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CIVIL ENGINEERING (STRUCTURES)**

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CERTIFICATION

I, Nwagwu, Chimaobi Onyedikachi, with registration number 20121797373, hereby certify that this project, titled “Prediction of Compressive Strength of cement blended Fly Ash-Periwinkle Shell Ash Sandcrete Blocks”, is original to me and has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of degree.

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APPROVAL

This research project, “Prediction of Compressive Strength of cement blended Fly Ash-Periwinkle Shell Ash Sandcrete Blocks”, by Nwagwu, Chimaobi Onyedikachi, with registration number 20121797373, is hereby approved as a satisfactory project for the award Bachelor of Engineering (B. Eng.) degree in Civil Engineering (Structures).

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DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated most importantly, to the Almighty Father, Christ the King, and the gentle Advocate in the Most Holy Trinity for all the mercies, favours, and graces received, and to my ever-supporting parents, Mr. & Mrs. Augustine Nwagwu, who have contributed so much to ensure that I had quality education.

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ABSTRACT

This study centred on the development of a mathematical model for the prediction of the compressive strength of cement blended Fly Ash-Periwinkle shell ash sandcrete blocks using Scheffe's simplex lattice. A total of ninety (90) fly ash-PSA solid sandcrete blocks of dimensions 450 x 125 x 225 mm were cast, consisting of three (3) blocks per mix ratio and for a total of thirty (30) mix ratios, comprising of fifteen (15) mix ratios each for both trial and control mixes. The first fifteen (15) mixes were used to develop the model while the other fifteen (15) were used to validate the model. The blocks were cured for 28 days by sprinkling of water. A computer program was written for Scheffe's model using Visual Basic 6.0. The program was used to predict the compressive strength for a given mix ratio and vice versa. The mathematical model results compared favourably with the experimental results. The model predictions were tested using statistical Students t-Test at 95% confidence level, and were found to be adequate. The optimum compressive strength of the blended sandcrete after 28 days of curing was found to be 3.9175 N/mm² which gave a corresponding mix ratio of 0.675, 1.19, 0.0375, 0.0225, 6.25 for water, cement, periwinkle shell ash, fly ash, and sand respectively.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

High cost of cement has become a problem in the construction industry in developing countries like Nigeria. Most of the researchers in this industry are doing their utmost best to minimize cost of cement and other construction materials by harnessing available local materials in the area.

Sandcrete is a blend of cement, sand, and water. Sandcrete blocks are the most commonly used unit in wall construction in modern Nigeria and, indeed, the entire West Africa. The use of laterite and other forms of walling units, for the construction of modern residential buildings have not made much progress when compared to the use of sandcrete blocks. The same can also be said of bricks. The major advantage of sandcrete blocks is the ease of production and laying of the blocks. The blocks are self-supporting; hence they are often referred to as zero slump concrete. Individual blocks are joined together, after curing, to form walls using cement-sand mortar. Recent studies involve partially replacing the cement portion with pozzolanic substances like fly ash, snail shell ash or periwinkle shell ash, and/or the sand portion with other materials such as laterite, coarse aggregate or quarry dust.

Intensified local economic ventures in many Nigerian communities have led to increased industrial and agricultural/plant wastes such as fly ash and periwinkle shell. On one hand, fly ash is a residue left from burning coal, which is collected on an electrostatic precipitator or in a baghouse. Economically, it makes sense to use as much of this low-cost ash as possible, especially if it can be used in sandcrete as a substitute for cement. Fly ash is pozzolanic, which means it is a siliceous and aluminous material that reacts with calcium hydroxide to form cement. On the other hand, periwinkle shell is a waste product generated from the consumption of a small greenish-blue marine snail (periwinkle), housed in a V shaped spiral shell, found in many coastal communities within Nigeria and is known worldwide to be a very strong, hard and brittle material. When subjected to a heating and crushing process, periwinkle shell ash (PSA) is formed.

It is in view of this that this experimental study seeks to investigate the suitability of fly ash and periwinkle shell ash as partial replacement for cement in sandcrete production as well as to develop a mathematical model that will ease the prediction of compressive strength of blended cement sandcrete.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Most sandcrete blocks are moulded using Ordinary Portland Cement being the most common and highly reliable type of cement. The increase in cost of cement has made building construction very expensive and seeming almost unaffordable.

Furthermore, cement manufacture causes environmental impacts with release of pollutants in the form of dust, greenhouse gases, and noise.

However, the use of fly ash and periwinkle shell ash as replacement of supplementary cementitious materials can help curb or at least reduce these problems by providing cheaper sandcrete, manage industrial/agricultural wastes and mitigate against pollution.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The main objective of this study was to predict the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks using Scheffe's simplex lattice. The specific objectives of the study were:

- i. To characterize fly ash and periwinkle shell ash.
- ii. To experimentally determine the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks at different percentage replacement of cement with fly ash and PSA respectively.
- iii. To formulate mathematical model for prediction of compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks.
- iv. To compare the compressive strength of sandcrete blocks predicted by the mathematical model and that obtained experimentally.
- v. To test for the adequacy of the model.
- vi. To develop a computer program that can easily predict the compressive strength of the sandcrete given a mix ratio and vice versa.
- vii. To determine the optimum compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

This study is important in that:

- i. It is intended to proffer solution to the current inadequate and unsafe waste disposal of industrial and agricultural wastes like fly ash and periwinkle shell by employing waste reusability as an alternative to help reduce environmental pollution thereby ensuring conservation of natural resources.
- ii. It will help engineers, researchers, and builders to predict compressive strength of blocks made from cement, sand, fly ash, and periwinkle shell ash, if their compressive strengths are known or vice versa.
- iii. It will reduce the problem of computing mix ratio of sandcrete blocks made from fly ash and periwinkle shell ash since the developed model can predict mix ratios of the block when their compressive strengths are known.

1.5 SCOPE OF STUDY

This research work is limited to prediction of compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks using the Scheffe's simplex lattice. This involves:

- i. Determination of the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks in the laboratory.
- ii. Development of a mathematical model capable of predicting the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks if the mix ratio is known or vice versa.
- iii. Checking the adequacy of the model.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 SANDCRETE BLOCKS

Sandcrete blocks are composite materials made up of cement, sand and water, moulded into different sizes. Nigerian Industrial Standard (NIS): 87-2004 defined sandcrete as a composite material made up of water, cement and sand. It differs from concrete in terms of material composition because of the non-inclusion of coarse aggregate in the mix, and differs from mortar in that the slump is zero. As a matter of fact, sandcrete is often referred to as zero slump concrete.

Sandcrete blocks are by far the most common type of block used in modern day construction in Nigeria. The major constituents are water, cement, and sand. The sand, according to the NIS 87: (2004) “shall be river, crushed or pit sand, clean and sharp and free from loam, dirt, organic or chemical matter of any description.” Their major advantages as compared to the other types of block are their easy mode of production and the speed of laying them. Their major setback is obviously their poor thermal and hygrometric properties. This can greatly affect their durability especially when they are permanently exposed to the elements. To improve these properties, the walls formed with sandcrete blocks are normally rendered with cement-sand mortar.

Sandcrete blocks are classified as solid or hollow blocks. Hollow blocks have cavities in them while the solid ones have no cavities. The length, width and height of the major sizes of sandcrete blocks produced in Nigeria are as follows:

- i. 450 x 225 x 225mm (hollow)
- ii. 450 x 150 x 225mm (hollow)
- iii. 450 x 150 x 225mm (solid)
- iv. 450 x 125 x 225mm (solid).

The 450 x 125 x 225mm solid blocks, which were cast in the course of the laboratory work of this research, are usually used for raising walls in buildings.

2.2 CONSTITUENTS OF SANDCRETE BLOCKS

Sandcrete blocks are traditionally made of a mixture of water, cement and sand (fine aggregates). Recent practice in sandcrete block production often includes the partial replacement of the sand with quarry dust or with coarse aggregates. This has been found to improve the strength and water absorption properties of the blocks (Anya, 2015).

2.2.1 Cement

Cement plays an indispensable role in concrete production as it is the main material that binds the constituents into a compact whole (Shetty, 2005 and Neville, 2011). It is a product resulting from the burning at very high temperatures (1300-1500°C) of certain proportions of ground calcareous materials such as limestone or chalk and argillaceous materials like clay or shale. The materials fuse into balls called clinker which is allowed to cool. The cooled clinker is then ground with gypsum added to improve its properties. The resulting product is called Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and is in the form of fine powder which, when mixed with water, forms a paste. OPC is the most common type of cement used in everyday construction works. Table 2.1 and Table 2.2. respectively show the major compounds and oxides in a typical Portland cement. Many other types of cement can be produced from OPC by doing any or combinations of the following:

- i. finer grinding of the clinker,
- ii. adding other chemicals such as calcium chloride,
- iii. altering the quantities of the oxides or compounds (see Tables 2.1 and 2.2) in the cement,
- iv. blending OPC intimately with Portland blast furnace slag.

The other types of cement include: Rapid hardening cement, Sulphate resisting cement, Low heat cement, Extra rapid hardening cement etc.

Table 2.1: Main compounds in Ordinary Portland Cement

Name of compound	Oxide composition/formula	Abbreviation
Tricalcium silicate	$3\text{CaO}.\text{SiO}_2$	C_3S
Dicalcium silicate	$2\text{CaO}.\text{SiO}_2$	C_2S
Tricalcium aluminate	$3\text{CaO}.\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	C_3A
Tetracalcium aluminoferrite	$4\text{CaO}.\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3.\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$	C_4AF

Source: Neville (2011) and Shetty (2005)

Table 2.2: Oxide composition of a typical Ordinary Portland cement

Oxide	Content (in percentage)
CaO	60 – 67
SiO ₂	17- 25
Al ₂ O ₃	3 – 8
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.5 - 6
MgO	0.5 - 4
Alkalis (as Na ₂ O)	0.3 -1.2
SO ₃	2.0 - 3.5

Source: Neville (2011)

Physical and chemical changes of the compounds occur when cement is mixed with water. This process is known as hydration of the cement. It is through this process that the cement-water paste becomes a firm and hard binding mass. During this process, the paste initially sets (stiffens) and hardens (gain strength) with time. The different compounds hydrate at different rates, produce heat over different lengths of time thus contributing differently to the rate of strength development of the hydrated cement. Cement properties can greatly be altered by the presence of moisture or on exposure to air. It is for this reason that it is advised that cement should always be stored in a dry place and should never be exposed to the air and the elements.

2.2.2 Fine aggregates

Aggregates are inert filler and generally constitute at least three-quarters of the volume of sandcrete. This percentage is even greater in mixes for sandcrete block production, especially for lean mixes. Because aggregates are cheaper than cement, it is advantageous to pack as much aggregate in the sandcrete as possible. Such high aggregate content “confers considerable technical advantages on the concrete, which has a higher volume stability and better durability than hydrated paste alone” (Neville, 2011).

Aggregates are classified in many ways as follows:

- i. According to size (i.e. fine and coarse aggregates)
- ii. According to source (i.e. natural and artificial aggregates)
- iii. According to weight (i.e. lightweight and dense aggregate)

- iv. According to particle shape (i.e. rounded, irregular, angular, and flaky)
- v. According to particle gradation (i.e. into well graded, poorly graded, and gap graded).

Fine aggregates are generally those whose particle sizes fall below 5mm while coarse aggregates are those with particle sizes greater than 5mm. The recent British and European standard (BS EN 12620, 2002) however, puts the dividing line between fine and coarse aggregates at 4mm. Natural aggregates are those formed from naturally occurring materials such as weathering of rocks and include sand, gravel, and crushed rock such as granite, basalt, sandstone and quartzite. Artificial aggregates, on the other hand, are manufactured and include sintered fly ash, aluminum slag and bloated clay. Lightweight aggregates have oven-dry particle density less than 2000kg/m³ while those with densities greater than 3000kg/m³ are classified as heavy weight aggregates. In between these two lie the medium weight aggregate (BS EN 206-1, 2000).

A well graded aggregate is one that contains all the different sizes in appropriate ratios. Such aggregates make better concrete as the smaller sized particles can always fill the spaces between the bigger ones, thus creating a more compact structure. Again they make the sandcrete more workable. Gap graded aggregates have some sizes missing while poorly graded aggregates have disproportionate ratios of the sizes. Both do not make for the “best” sandcrete in terms of strength and workability.

Gradation or particle size distribution of fine aggregates is of great importance in the manufacture of sandcrete blocks. This gradation is obtained through a sieve analysis in which a certain amount of the aggregate is passed through a set of stacked sieves successively arranged with the one having the largest aperture at the top. The result of the sieve analysis is put in the form of a gradation curve from which the coefficient of uniformity C_u and the coefficient of gradation, C_c are determined. C_u and C_c are given in Equations (2.1) and (2.2):

$$C_u = \frac{D_{60}}{D_{10}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$C_c = \frac{D_{30}^2}{D_{10}D_{60}} \quad (2.2)$$

where D_{10} , D_{30} , and D_{60} are particle size diameters corresponding to 10, 30 and 60%, respectively passing on the cumulative size distribution (gradation) curve. D_{10} is often referred to as the effective size of the aggregate.

Another parameter also often used in describing the distribution is the fineness modulus. The fineness modulus is an empirical index of coarseness or fineness of the aggregate obtained by the addition of the cumulative percentages of aggregate retained on each of the standard sieves. Fineness modulus between 2.3 and 3.1 is suitable for concrete works. Rounded aggregates give a more workable mix. Angular aggregates make concrete harder to place, work and compact, but can make concrete stronger. Flaky aggregates are not good for concrete works. The desirable aggregate for concrete works is well graded, inert, well textured, shaped and hard (Anya, 2015).

2.2.3 Water

Water plays an indispensable role in sandcrete production. Both the quality and quantity of the water is of great importance. Water is needed during the mixing process and also during the curing period. The quantity of water used in sandcrete production is usually expressed in relation to the cement content, hence the term ‘water/cement (w/c) ratio’. This ratio must be carefully controlled as it greatly affects the strength, workability and durability of the sandcrete. A very low w/c ratio will lead to poor hydration of the cement resulting in reduced strength and low durability. The workability of the concrete will also be poor. Very high ratios also have similar end effects, as the sandcrete will even flow.

The quality of the water is often not given enough attention during sandcrete production. Many dissolved solids and suspended solids in water may greatly affect the quality and strength of the concrete. The Cement and Concrete Association of Australia (2002) recommends the mixing water for concrete/sandcrete to be potable and this is the generally accepted quality for water used in concrete production. In some instances, there may be more stringent restrictions placed on mixing water. Impurities that if in high concentration in water may make the water not suitable for sandcrete/concrete production include chlorides, suspended solid and sodium sulphate. Allowable maximum amount of impurities in mixing water is given in BS EN 1008 (2002) and ASTM C-1602 (2006). Water with pH value less than 6 or higher than 9 is also not acceptable for sandcrete production.

Sea water contains high level of chloride which can lead to rapid corrosion of the steel reinforcement bars especially when the sandcrete is porous and no adequate cover is provided for the reinforcement bars. Since these factors cannot always be taken care of, it is advisable to avoid making reinforced concrete with sea water (Shetty, 2005). The requirement of water for concrete

curing is less stringent. However, the water should not contain impurities, dissolved or suspended which will stain or attack the hardened sandcrete. For instance, water with high amount of iron if used for curing could impair the appearance of the sandcrete.

2.3 PROPERTIES OF SANDCRETE

There are a number of properties possessed by sandcrete, a few of which are discussed here.

2.3.1 Compressive strength

The compressive strength is by far the most important strength property used to judge the overall quality of sandcrete. It may often be the only strength property of the sandcrete that may be determined since with a few exceptions almost all the properties of sandcrete can be related to its compressive strength. Compressive strength is usually determined by subjecting the hardened sandcrete, after appropriate curing, usually for 28 days, to increasing compressive load until it fails by crushing, and determining the crushing force. Mathematically, compressive strength is expressed as in Equation (2.3):

$$f_c = \frac{F}{A} \quad (2.3)$$

where f_c = compressive strength (N/mm²)

F = crushing load (N)

A = cross-sectional area of the test specimen (mm²)

Many research works done to determine the compressive strength of commercially available sandcrete blocks produced at various locations in Nigeria show very disappointing results. For example, Mahmoud et al. (2010) carried out tests on both 450 x 225 x 225 and 450 x 225 x 150 mm blocks from five different manufacturers in Yola, Northern Nigeria. They found that their strength ranged from 0.31 N/mm² to 1.36N/mm² and 0.12 N/mm² to 1.46N/mm² respectively. These values are far below the minimum recommended values of NIS 87: (2004). The results obtained by Mahmoud et al (2010) merely corroborated those previously obtained by Abdullahi (2005), and Banuso and Ejeh (2008) who, respectively, investigated the compressive strengths of commercially produced sandcrete blocks in Minna and Kaduna, both prominent cities in Northern

Nigeria. Similar poor results were obtained in Southern Nigeria. These are detailed in works by Olufisayo (2013), Okere (2012), Anosike and Oyebande (2012), and Umenwaliri and Ezenwamma (2008).

2.3.2 Workability

This refers to the ease with which concrete/sandcrete can be compacted fully without segregating and bleeding (Bhavikatti, 2010). He further defined workability as the amount of internal work required to fully compact concrete/sandcrete to optimum density. According to Neville (2010), workability is the amount of useful internal work necessary to produce full compaction. Workability depends upon the quantity of water, grading, shape, and percentage of fine aggregates present in the sandcrete. It is measured by:

- i. the slump observed when the frustum of standard cone, filled with sandcrete and the mixture compacted, is turned upside down and lifted/removed.
- ii. the compaction factor determined after allowing the sandcrete to fall through the compacting testing machine.
- iii. the time taken (in seconds) for the shape of the sandcrete to change from a cone to cylinder when tested in Vee-Bee consistometer.

2.3.3 Bleeding

This refers to the appearance of water along the cement particles on the surface of the freshly laid sandcrete/concrete. Separation of water in this manner is known as bleeding (Dhir and Jackson, 1996). This happens when there is excessive quantity of water in the mix or due to excessive compaction. Bleeding causes the formation of pores and renders the sandcrete weak. Bleeding can be avoided by adequately controlling the quantity of water in the sandcrete and by using finer grading of fine aggregates.

2.3.4 Harshness

This is the resistance offered by sandcrete/concrete to its surface finish. Harshness is due to the presence of lesser quantity of fine aggregates, lesser cement mortar and as a result of use of poorly graded aggregates. It may also result due to insufficient quantity of water (Bhavikatti, 2010). Harsh sandcrete hardly has a smooth surface finish and is likely to be porous.

2.3.5 Durability

Durability is that property of sandcrete that requires it to “continue to perform its intended functions, that is, maintain its strength and serviceability, during the specified or expected service life” (Neville, 2011). Shetty (2005) defined durability of concrete/sandcrete as “its ability to resist weathering action, chemical attacks, abrasion, or any other process of deterioration.” The durability of the sandcrete can be affected by chemical attack through the actions of aggressive ions such as chlorides, sulphates and many other natural or industrial liquids and gases. Physical factors such as high temperatures and thermal expansion of the aggregates in the hardened sandcrete can also lead to extensive deterioration of the sandcrete. Much emphasis is placed on the strength properties of sandcrete than any other property as durability. This may be because the strength properties usually provide a better picture on the quality of the sandcrete. However, there may be some situations when durability and other considerations may be of greater importance (Neville, 2011). Durable sandcrete is dense, water tight and able to resist, to a reasonable extent, changes resulting from adverse effects of the elements and mechanical damage.

There are many properties that are used as an indicator of the durability of concrete/sandcrete. Most of these are based on the permeability of the hardened concrete/sandcrete (Long et al, 2001, Basheer et al, 1994, Neville, 2011). One of such properties is water absorption test in which a totally dry sandcrete sample is completely immersed in water for say, 24 hours. The difference between the weight before and after immersion, expressed as a percentage of the dry weight, gives the percentage water absorption. Mathematically, the water absorption is given in Equation (2.4):

$$w_a = \frac{w_d - w_s}{w_d} \times 100\% \quad (2.4)$$

where w_a = water absorption

w_d = dry weight of specimen

w_s = weight of specimen after soaking in water for 24 hours

NIS 87 (2004) recommends that sandcrete blocks should have water absorption not greater than 6%.

2.4 PRODUCTION PROCESS OF SANDCRETE BLOCKS

The production of sandcrete blocks can be discussed under the following sub-headings:

- i. Batching and Mixing
- ii. Compaction and Demoulding
- iii. Curing
- iv. Storage

2.4.1 Batching and Mixing

Batching is the process of measuring out the various quantities of the components. This can be done by mass or by volume. Of the two, batching by mass is professionally preferable as it eliminates errors due to the variations contained in a specific volume. However, most producers, especially those that batch manually, use the volume batching process because it is simpler and much more convenient than weight batching.

Manual batching is done using head pans, wheel barrows or specially constructed wooden gauge boxes with a bag of cement taken to be twice the volume of a head pan and the same volume as a wheel barrow. The use of the wooden boxes for batching is becoming obsolete. Cement is usually supplied in bags of 50kg net weight. Batching using head pans or wheel barrows does not make for uniformity as these volumes measured are greatly dependent on the state and size of the head pans or wheel barrows. It should be noted that sand is usually supplied wet and it is in this wet condition that it is most often used. The quantity of water added to the mix must therefore be adjusted to compensate for the water in the wet sand. Furthermore, since sandcrete is a zero slump concrete, the amount of mixing water added is of great importance. Too little or too much water will cause the block to fail immediately after demoulding.

Mixing is done either manually (with shovels or spades) or mechanically (using concrete mixers of various capacities). Large producers generally use mixers. This offers a more uniform and homogenous mix, especially when the volume is large. In manual mixing the components are mixed using shovels or spades and turned over several times until a homogenous mix is obtained. Whatever method is adopted, adequate mixing is necessary to achieve uniform colour and texture between block batches, prevent variations in strength and minimize web cracks (Portland Cement Association, 1975).

2.4.2 Compaction and Demoulding

Compaction is a very important process in block production. Compaction is achieved by mechanical vibration or manual (hand) compaction. Manual compaction is less effective and is adopted by small scale producers. One block is produced at a time using a locally manufactured mould. The compaction is effected using a tamping rod. Great care is needed in demoulding the block in order not to introduce cracks in it.

There are basically three types of machines used in block moulding in Nigeria. Some of these in addition to compaction also vibrate the blocks. The machine type greatly affects the quality and the required water used in the block production. The three major types of machines are:

- i. Egg-laying machine
- ii. Electric vibrating machine
- iii. Manual hand press machine

(i) Egg-laying machine: The egg-laying machines are usually of the Rosa Commetta type that can lay up to ten blocks at a time. This is usually used for mass production and the process can be automated, leading to great hourly output of about 300 -500 blocks. Both pressure and vibration are applied and blocks of high quality can be produced with these machines. The blocks are usually laid on bare surfaces without pallets and are removed for storage after 2-3 days of production.

(ii) Electric vibrating machines: These machines are commonly used by medium scale producers. They are electrically operated or diesel powered. The majority of the machines are designed to produce one block at a time with the block vibrated for about 10 to 15 seconds. Few, however, can produce up to three blocks at a time. The blocks are produced on pallets and carried to the place of temporary storage. They can provide adequate compaction. Care must be taken while moving the blocks on the pallet to the place of temporary storage so as to prevent cracks resulting from vibration while moving the blocks.

(iii) Manual hand press machine: The hand press machine is manually operated. Demoulding is achieved through a series of levers. The hand press machine does not compact as well as the egg laying and vibrating machines and hence produces blocks of lower quality. One block is moulded at a time.

2.4.3 Curing

Curing of sandcrete blocks is necessary to enable the blocks develop adequate or optimum strength by allowing for proper hydration of the cement. Green blocks that are exposed to high temperatures lose water rapidly by evaporation, resulting in weak blocks. Thus it is recommended that newly produced blocks be placed in covered shades and protected from the adverse effect of the elements. Works by Uzomaka (1977) and Rahman (1968) suggest curing by sprinkling with water as the best method of curing, from strength and convenience point of view. This is the most common method employed by commercial block producers. Sprinkling should be done at least once in a day. NIS 87 (2004) requires that the blocks be left on the pallets for at least 24 hours and be cured for at least 3 days. Adequate care must be taken when removing the pallets for another production so that cracks are not induced in the blocks.

2.4.4 Storage

Cured blocks are removed to storage to provide space for new productions. The blocks need adequate care at this stage. Many blocks are normally damaged at this stage due to poor handling. NIS 87: (2004) requires that the blocks be stacked not more than 5 courses high. The blocks are now ready for use.

2.5 FACTORS AFFECTING THE STRENGTH OF SANDCRETE BLOCKS

The factors that affect the quality and strength of sandcrete blocks can be divided into those related to the quality and relative proportions of the constituents, and those related to the manufacturing process. Only a brief discussion of some of these factors will be made here as they have been indirectly discussed in the previous sections.

2.5.1 Factors related to the quality and relative proportions of the constituents

Of interest here are aggregate gradation, cement /aggregate ratio, and water/cement ratio. Aggregate gradation has a great influence on both the strength and physical properties of the blocks. The ideal gradation is a well graded aggregate which will provide a dense pack where spaces between the big particles will be filled by the smaller ones. Such gradation also makes for minimum volume change due to shrinkage. Poorly graded or gap graded aggregate produce less dense blocks and may also be less workable.

The cement/aggregate ratio is one of the most important factors affecting the strength of blocks. An increase in this ratio leads to an increase in strength. Gooding and Thomas (1997) showed that whereas doubling the compaction effort produced a 23% increase in compressive strength of sandcrete blocks, doubling the cement content produced a whopping 140% increase. NIS 87: (2004) recommends cement/sand ratio of 1:6 for sandcrete block production.

The water/cement ratio is very important in sandcrete block production. Unlike concrete which is allowed to set in forms, sandcrete blocks are demoulded immediately after compaction. This greatly reduces the range of water/cement ratio over which the blocks can be made. The water/cement ratio should be such that allows for proper hydration of the cement yet allowing the green blocks to stand unsupported after demoulding. Uzomaka (1975) gave suitable water/cement ratios for block production as ranging from 0.4 to 0.6. Like concrete, strength of blocks is known to decrease with increase in water/cement ratio. Too dry a mix will lead to fracture during demoulding while high water/cement ratio will cause shrinkage and distortion in blocks (Tyler, 1961).

2.5.2 Factors related to the manufacturing process

The two most important factors here are the degree of compaction and the curing process. Omoregie (2012) showed that the strength of sandcrete blocks is improved with better compaction. The degree of compaction is greatly dependent on the type of moulding machine used. Umenwaliri and Ezenwamma (2008) studied the effect of production methods on the strength of sandcrete blocks and concluded that the production method (compaction) affects the strength of the blocks. Strength of vibrated block is improved when additional surcharge is provided. It should be noted, however, that increasing compaction does not necessarily imply a more economic production (Gooding and Thomas, 1997).

2.6 POZZOLANS

A pozzolan is defined as a siliceous or siliceous and aluminous material that in itself possesses little or no cementitious value, but that will, in finely divided form and in the presence of moisture, chemically react with calcium hydroxide at ordinary temperatures to form compounds having cementitious properties (Shetty, 2005). Pozzolans that are commonly used in concrete include fly ash, silica fume and a variety of natural pozzolans such as calcined clay and shale, and volcanic

ash. Before the advent of cement, pozzolans were used with lime to make concrete. Currently, their principal use is to replace a proportion in cement when producing concrete/sandcrete. The advantages gain numerous including:

- i. Economy
- ii. Improvement in workability of concrete/sandcrete mix
- iii. Reduction in bleeding and segregation
- iv. Greater protection against freezing and thawing
- v. Better protection against sulphate attack
- vi. Reduction in disruptive effects of alkali-aggregate reaction and heat of hydration
- vii. Reduction in leaching of soluble compounds from sandcrete/concrete
- viii. Impermeability of sandcrete/concrete at later ages.

The main justification for using pozzolans however, is the possibility of reducing costs. If they are to reduce costs, they must be obtained locally and it is for this reason that they have not so much been in use so far.

2.6.1 Classification of Pozzolans

Pozzolans can either be naturally-occurring or artificial. Most naturally-occurring pozzolans are derived from volcanic activity. During an explosive volcanic eruption, quick cooling of the magma, composed mainly of aluminosilicates, results in the formation of glass or vitreous phases with a disordered structure. During the solidifying of the magma however, the evolution of gases causes a porous texture and high surface area in the resulting rock. This enhances the chemical reactivity of this resultant rock. Aluminosilicates with a distorted structure are unstable in alkaline solutions, thus the high reactivity of volcanic glasses with lime or Portland cement in an aqueous environment.

Artificial pozzolans are those produced as byproducts/wastes either from industrial, agricultural and/or laboratory activities. Some examples include snail shell ash, periwinkle shell ash, coconut shell ash, fly ash etc.

2.6.2 The Activity of Pozzolans

When the pozzolan is mixed with Ordinary Portland Cement, the silica of the pozzolan combines with free lime released during the hydration of cement. This action is known as the pozzolanic

action. The pozzolanic activity is due to the presence of finely divided glassy silica hydrate similar to that produced during hydration of Portland cement. The silica in the pozzolan reacts with the lime produced during the hydration of Portland cement and contributes to strength development. Slowly and gradually, additional calcium silicate hydrate is formed which is a binder and fills up the space, ensures impermeability, durability, and ever-increasing strength.

Silica of amorphous form react readily with lime than those of crystalline form, and this constitutes the difference between active pozzolans and materials of similar chemical composition which exhibit little pozzolanic activity. Since pozzolanic action can proceed only in the presence of water, enough moisture has to be made available for a long time to complete pozzolanic action. It is commonly thought that lime-silica reaction is the main reaction or even the only one that takes place, but recent information indicates that alumina and iron, if present, also take part in the chemical reaction. The optimum amount of pozzolan as replacement for cement may normally range between 10% to 30% and may be as low as 4% to 6% for natural pozzolans.

2.7 FLY ASH

Fly ash is a fine powder which is a byproduct from burning pulverized coal in electric generation power plants. Fly ash is used as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in the production of sandcrete/concrete. A supplementary cementitious material, when used in conjunction with Portland cement, contributes to the properties of the hardened sandcrete through hydraulic or pozzolanic activity, or both. As such, SCM's include both pozzolans and hydraulic materials. SCM's that are hydraulic in behavior include ground granulated blast furnace slag and fly ashes with high calcium contents (such fly ashes display both pozzolanic and hydraulic behavior).

The potential for using fly ash as a supplementary cementitious material in concrete/sandcrete has been known almost since the start of the last century (Anon, 1914), although it was not until the mid-1900s that significant utilization of fly ash in concrete/sandcrete began (for example, USBR, 1948) following the pioneering research conducted at the University of California, Berkeley (Davis, 1937). The last 50 years has seen the use of fly ash in concrete grow dramatically with close to 15 million tons used in concrete, concrete products and grouts in the U.S. in 2005 (ACAA, 2006).

Historically, fly ash has been used in concrete/sandcrete at levels ranging from 15% to 25% by mass of the cementitious material component. The actual amount used varies widely depending on the application, the properties of the fly ash, specification limits, and the geographic location and climate. Higher levels (30% to 50%) have been used in massive structures (for example, foundations and dams) to control temperature rise. In recent decades, research has demonstrated that high dosage levels (40% to 60%) can be used in structural applications, producing concrete/sandcrete with good mechanical properties and durability (Marceau, 2002).

Increasing the amount of fly ash for replacing cement is not without shortcomings. At high levels problems may be encountered with extended set times and slow strength development, leading to low early-age strengths and delays in the rate of construction. These drawbacks become particularly pronounced in cold-weather concreting. Also, the durability of the concrete/sandcrete may be compromised with regards to resistance to deicer-salt scaling and carbonation.

For any given situation there will be an optimum amount of fly ash that can be used in a concrete/sandcrete mixture which will maximize the technical, environmental, and economic benefits of fly ash use without significantly impacting the rate of construction or impairing the long-term performance of the finished product. The optimum amount of fly ash will be a function of wide range of parameters and must be determined on a case-by-case basis. Figure 2.1 attempts to show the process involved in the fly ash production at electric generation plants.

Figure 2.1: Schematic layout of a coal-fired electrical generating station (Sear, 2001)

Classes of fly ash

There are two (2) classes of fly ash. They are Class F and Class C.

Class F fly ash is made from burning anthracite and/or bituminous coal. It is used at dosages of 15% to 25% by mass of cementitious material. It greatly reduces the risk of expansion due to sulphate attack as may occur in fertilized soils or near coastal areas. Class F are generally low-calcium fly ashes with carbon contents less than 5% but sometimes as high as 10%.

Class C fly ash is produced from lignite or subbituminous coal. It is used at dosages of 15% to 40% by mass of cementitious material. It is also resistant to expansion from chemical attack, has a higher percentage of calcium oxide, and is more commonly used for structural concrete. Class C fly ashes are typically composed of high-calcium with carbon contents less than 2%.

2.8 PERIWINKLE SHELL ASH (PSA)

PSA is obtained by burning periwinkle shell to sustained high temperatures. The residue may then be grinded to the desired size. Periwinkle is described as any small greenish marine snail from the class of gastropod, the largest of the seven classes in the phylum mollusk (Olorunoje and Olalusi, 2003). They are herbivorous and found on rocks, stones or pilings between high and low tide marks; on mud-flats as well as on prop roots of mangrove trees and in fresh and salt water.

The common periwinkle (with botanical name: *Littorina littorea*) is one of the most abundant marine gastropods in the North Atlantic, but a different specie (with botanical name: *Tympanotonus fuscatus*) is commonly found in the estuaries and mangrove swamp forest of the Niger Delta of the South – South region of Nigeria (Badmus et al, 2007). A study (Mmom and Arokoya, 2010) indicated that there are about 40.3 tonnes of periwinkle per year being harvested from 35 mangrove communities of Delta and Rivers states of Nigeria. A survey, by the researchers, of some riverside communities of Itu, Oron, Issiet, Okobo, Ikot Offiong, and Uta-eweia in Akwa Ibom state showed abundance of periwinkle in these communities. Massive periwinkle harvesting is also reported from some communities in Bayelsa, Cross River and Edo states of Nigeria (Jamabo and Chinda, 2010). When the periwinkle is big enough, the edible part is removed after boiling in water, and the shell dumped as waste. The continuous dumping of the shells (Job et al, 2009) has

resulted in great heaps constituting menace especially in villages in Rivers and Akwa Ibom states of Nigeria.

Periwinkles are considered a delicacy in African and Asian cuisines. The meat is high in protein, omega-3 fatty acids and low in fat; according to the USDA National Nutrient Database for Standard Reference, raw snails in general are about 80% water, 15% protein, and 1.4% fat. Periwinkles are also used as bait for catching small fish. The shell is usually crushed and the soft parts extracted and put on a hook.

Raising the common periwinkle has not been a focus due to its abundance in nature and relatively low price, however there are potential benefits from aquaculturing this species, including a more controlled environment, easier harvesting, less damages from predators, as well as saving the natural population from commercial harvesting.

2.9 OPTIMIZATION MODEL

Optimization model is the model used to find the best possible choice out of a set of alternatives. It may use the mathematical expression of a problem to maximize or minimize some function. The alternatives are frequently restricted by constraints on the values of the variables. A simple example might be finding the most efficient transport system to carry commodities from the point of supply to the markets, given the volumes of production and demand, together with unit transport costs. A model in optimization modelling must have decision goal and constraints. In civil engineering, prediction of sandcrete/concrete strength has been an active area of research and a considerable number of studies have been carried out.

Traditionally, concrete/sandcrete mix optimization is based on a trial and error basis in which adjustments, in proportions of the components, are made to a given set of mix ratios until a product of the desired characteristics (compressive strength, water absorption, tensile strength, workability, or any other desired property) is achieved. When the number of constituents is small, the process can be less tedious and cost effective. However, as the number of constituents increases, the problem of identifying optimum mixes to meet the desired properties becomes more complex as the number of trial mixes becomes prohibitive especially when several performance criteria are considered (Simon, 2003). The use of experimentally designed methodologies, in such cases, greatly reduces the amount of experimental work ((Akhnazarova and Kafarov, 1982). One other

obvious setback of the traditional method (Simon, 2003) is that it does not account for the interactions among the sandcrete/concrete constituents and there is no means to achieve an efficiently optimized mixture for a given criterion. The problems associated with the traditional method can be overcome if a statistical approach in which, rather than starting with one trial mix, a set of trial mixes covering over a chosen range of proportion of the constituents is employed and statistical methods used in analyzing the results (Simon, 2003). The end result is a mathematical model which can predict the response (the property) given a set of proportions of the constituents that are within the specified range. Such models can be used to do many analyses and can even be used to determine the proportions of the constituents to yield a desired property. The application of statistical methods in concrete mixture experiments is becoming popular. When the problem involves data that are subject to experimental errors, statistical methods are the only objective approach to analysis (Montgomery, 2005). There are two approaches in statistical experimental methods, namely: Factorial designs and Mixture designs.

The objective in factorial designs is to observe the change in the response function to changes in the level of one or two factors while the levels of the other remain constant (Cornell, 2002). The main effects and interaction effects of the factors are obtained. The experimenter varies the controlled variables (factors) in a precise way so as to cause changes in a response variable. Mixture designs/experiments differ from this in that the controlled variable (ingredients or components) must add up to 1 or 100%. The amount of the controlled variable does not matter but the proportion of the total is of prime importance. When statistical design and analysis of experiments are desired, it is necessary to, as much as possible, observe the basic principles of experimental design, namely: randomization, replication, and blocking.

Randomization is one of the most important elements of a well-designed experiment. Randomization protects against confounding and can form the basis for inference (Oehlert, 2010). When statistical methods are employed, the observations or errors should be independently distributed random variables. By randomizing the experiment, materials allocation and the order in which the experimental runs are performed are randomly determined (Montgomery, 2005). Randomization helps to assist in averaging out or reducing the effects of factors which may not be explicitly accounted for during the experimental runs, and also on helping in meeting the assumptions of the statistical methods used in analyzing experiments.

Replication is an independent repeat of a run. It provides a means of measuring pure error, thus giving one the opportunity of determining if the observed differences in the data are statistically different (Montgomery, 2005). Blocking is the arrangement of experimental units in groups (blocks) that are similar. Blocking helps to reduce variability and thus lead to greater precision.

2.10 MIXTURE EXPERIMENT AND MODEL FORMS

A mixture experiment is one in which the response is assumed to be dependent on the relative proportions of the constituent materials and not on their total amount (Cornell, 2002). The constituents of the mixture can be measured by volume or mass. For such experiments, there are two basic requirements that must be satisfied namely; the sum of the proportions of the constituents must add up to 1 and none of the constituents will have a negative value.

Mixture models have been applied in many real life applications to solve problems in such areas as in pharmacy, food industry, agriculture and engineering. Piepel and Redgate (1998) applied mixture experiment analysis to determining oxide compositions in cement clinker. Ezeh et al (2010) developed a model for the optimization of aggregate composition of laterite/sand hollow block using Scheffe's simplex method. Mama and Osadebe (2011) developed models, one based on Scheffe's simplex lattice and the other on Osadebe's model, for predicting the compressive strength of sandcrete blocks using alluvial deposit. Osadebe's model was also used by Anyaogu et al (2013) to predict the compressive strength of Pulverized Fuel Ash (PFA) – Cement concrete. Some other works on mixture experiments include:

- i. Simon (2003) who developed models for concrete mixture optimization. Models were developed for many responses such as compressive strength, 1-day strength, slump and 42-day charge passed for concrete made using water, cement, silica fume, high range water-reducing admixture, coarse aggregate and fine aggregate.
- ii. Obam (2009) developed a model for optimizing shear modulus of Rice husk ash concrete.
- iii. Onwuka et al (2011) developed a model for prediction of concrete mix ratios using modified regression theory.
- iv. Osadebe and Ibearugbulem (2009) together developed a simplex lattice model for optimizing compressive strength of periwinkle shell-granite concrete.

- v. Ezeh (2009) and Ibearugbulem (2010) developed models for optimizing compressive strength of recycled concrete and river stone aggregate concrete respectively.
- vi. Akalin et al (2008) optimized chemical admixture for concrete on mortar performance tests.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS

The materials used for this work include:

- i. Ordinary Portland Cement
- ii. Water
- iii. River Sand
- iv. Fly ash
- v. Periwinkle shell ash

3.1.1 Ordinary Portland Cement

Cement in the general sense of the word can be described as a material with adhesive and cohesive properties which makes it capable of bonding material fragments into a compact whole. Dangote brand of Ordinary Portland cement, conforming to the requirements of BS 12:1978 with moisture content of 0.003 and specific gravity of 3.15, was purchased from a cement dealer at Eziobodo within FUTO community in Owerri West L.G.A of Imo state, Nigeria and stored in a dry place prior to use for all the tests.

3.1.2 Water

Water is one of the important materials for producing sandcrete blocks. Water is an important ingredient in sandcrete as it actively participates in the chemical reaction with cement, hence its quality and quantity should carefully be looked into. The criterion for portability of water is not absolute. Natural water which is slightly acidic is harmless, but water containing organic acids may adversely affect the hardening of sandcrete. Clean potable water, having pH value of 7, free from foreign materials obtained from a borehole supply, and conforming to the specification of EN 1008: (2002) was used for both specimen preparations and curing.

3.1.3 River Sand

Sharp river sand with bulk density of 2620kg/m³ and specific gravity of 2.62 was obtained from Otamiri, a nearby river along the Umuchima/Ihiagwa axis within FUTO community in Owerri West L.G.A of Imo State, Nigeria. As a medium for preparing the sand for use, the heap was spread

and exposed to air for several days to remove moisture in the particles. Excess moisture in the river sand would increase the water-cement ratio in sandcrete which will consequently give a wrong result of the finished specimen.

3.1.4 Fly ash

Fly ash was obtained from the coal electric power plant at Milking Hill in Enugu state, Nigeria. The ash was then prepared for use by grinding to fine powder and sieved with 150 μ m sieve to obtain roughly the fineness of cement. The total quantity of fly ash needed for this research work was about 6.5kg. Hence, about 16kg of fly ash was provided for grinding and sieving to produce about 10kg of fly ash so that the extra 3.5kg covered for losses in the course of the experiment.

3.1.5 Periwinkle shell ash

Periwinkle shells were collected from local markets at Ihiagwa within FUTU community in Owerri West L.G.A of Imo state, Nigeria. These shells were then prepared for use by first washing and drying thereby making the material free from any organic and inorganic matter. Thereafter, the shells were burned to very high temperatures exceeding 800°C. The ash was then grinded to fine powder and sieved with 150 μ m sieve to obtain roughly the fineness of cement. The total quantity of periwinkle shell ash needed for this research work was about 10kg. Hence, about 64kg of clean dry periwinkle shells were subjected to heating process to produce about 21kg of periwinkle shell ash. This quantity of PSA was then grinded and sieved to produce about 15kg of PSA so that the extra 5kg covered for losses in the course of the experiment.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.2.1 Sieve Analyses

Sieve analysis is a laboratory method used to determine the grain size distribution of aggregates. A stack of sieves was arranged with larger sieve sizes placed above the smaller ones. The sieve analyses were performed on both fly ash and periwinkle shell ash to determine the particle size distribution. The samples collected were all dried for seven days before conducting the sieve analyses. Sieve analysis was conducted on the fly ash first, and then on the PSA. The stack of sieves was subjected to vibration for about 10 to 15 minutes by the mechanical shaker to induce

the action of sorting the materials through the different sieves depending on the material particle size. The particles passing through the 150 μ m sieve were collected in a clean dry pan.

3.2.2 Chemical Tests on both Fly Ash and Periwinkle Shell Ash

Chemical tests were carried out on the fly ash and the PSA to ascertain the properties of the materials relevant to cement. The tests were conducted at Project Development Institute, PRODA, Emene, Enugu state, Nigeria.

Procedure

Pozzolanicity tests were carried out on both fly ash and PSA. The test on the fly ash was first conducted, and then that on the PSA was done but both tests followed the same process. 20g of the ash was mixed with a given volume of Ca(OH)₂ of known concentration. Samples of the mixture was then titrated against HCl solution of known concentration at time intervals of 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes, using phenolphthalein as indicator at normal temperature. The titre value was observed to reduce with time, confirming the ash as a pozzolan that fixed more and more of the calcium hydroxide, thereby reducing the alkalinity of the mixture. It was observed that both the fly ash and PSA contain all the main chemical constituents of cement in near percentage of all the constituents compared with that of Ordinary Portland Cement, which means they will serve as suitable replacements if the right percentage is used.

3.2.3 Slump test

Slump test is usually conducted in order to ascertain the workability of sandcrete/concrete mix. In this research work, slump test was performed on each batch for both trial and control mixes of the blended fly ash-PSA sandcrete.

Procedure

A frustum of cone (known as slump cone) 300mm in height was pressed upon a flat tray thereby forming a mould. Sandcrete mix was loaded into this mould using a scoop. The mix was compacted in four layers, 25 times each, using a tamping rod of 16mm diameter. After compaction, the mix was allowed to overflow the mould so that the tamping rod was used to level the top. The slump cone was then slowly and carefully lifted off the sandcrete just as a stopwatch was started. The stopwatch was allowed to read only 10 seconds and then stopped. After lifting the slump cone, the sandcrete subsided thus showing the difference in height between the height of the mould and that

of the highest point on the subsided sandcrete. The slump which is taken as the subsidence of the sandcrete was measured using a steel rule, and then recorded. This procedure was repeated for every other batch/mix.

3.2.4 Production of Sandcrete Specimen

The field work was on the production of the sandcrete blocks. The blocks to be tested for their compressive strength were moulded using the ratios already estimated. The blocks were produced using the locally manufactured mould which produces only one block at a time. Batching of the materials was done by mass using a weighing balance of 50kg capacity. Solid blocks of dimension 450 x 125 x 225 mm were moulded. Mixing of the constituents was done manually using shovels. First, the sand and the cement were mixed to a constant colour. Fly ash and PSA, which had been previously grinded and sieved, were then added and the whole process of mixing continued until a uniform colour was achieved. Water was finally added and the mixing continued until the colour of the paste was uniform. The mixture was then loaded into the mould where it was compacted by raising and dropping the loaded mould. The mould was then filled to the top, compacted and levelled using a tamping rod, and finally demoulded immediately. A total of 90 sandcrete blocks with partial replacement of cement with fly ash and PSA were produced. All 90 blocks were cured, under shade, for 28 days by sprinkling them daily with potable water obtained from a nearby borehole.

3.2.5 Compressive strength test

First, the blocks were weighed, using a 50kg capacity weighing balance, to ascertain the mass of each individual specimen. The mass values obtained were recorded, and later used to calculate the density of each block as would be explained later. The blocks were crushed after 28 days of curing using Okhard Machine Tool's WA-1000B digital display Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The machine conforms to the requirements of BS EN 12390-4 (2000) and has a testing range of 0 – 1000kN. The solid sandcrete blocks were placed in between two steel plates of 25mm thickness and wide enough as to cover the top and bottom of the blocks. Force was gradually applied through the platens of the testing machine until the blocks failed in compression. The values read off the UTM at failure of block represent the compressive load. The compressive strengths of the blocks were determined. With the cross-sectional area as an input, the machine displays both the crushing load and the stress at failure. Three samples each were tested for a particular mix ratio and the average value taken as the compressive strength for the mix.

3.3 ANALYTICAL METHODS

The use of simplex design and the regression analysis in the formulation of sandcrete design models was considered in detail in this work. Particularly however, the Scheffe's method of optimization was used in the modelling and optimization of compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete.

3.3.1 Scheffe's Optimization Model

In this work, Henry Scheffe's optimization model was used to develop models that will predict possible mix proportions of sandcrete components that will produce a desired compressive strength. Achieving a desired compressive strength of sandcrete is dependent to a large extent on the adequate proportioning of the components of the sandcrete. In Scheffe's work, the desired property of the various mix ratios depended on the proportion of the components present, but not on the quality of mixture. Therefore, if a mixture has a total of q components/ingredients of the i^{th} component of the mixture,

$$X_i \geq 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, q) \quad (3.1a)$$

Where X_i = the i^{th} component of the mixture and assuming the mixture to be a unit quantity, then the sum of all proportions of the component must be unity. That is,

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + \dots + X_q = 1 \quad (3.1b)$$

This implies that

$$\sum_{i=1}^q X_i = 1 \quad (3.2)$$

Combining Equations (3.1a) and (3.2) implies that:

$$0 \leq X_i \leq 1 \quad (3.3)$$

The factor space therefore is a regular $(q - 1)$ dimensional simplex.

3.3.1.1 Scheffe's Simplex Lattice

Simplex refers to a structural representation of a line or plane joining the assuming position of a constituent material of a mixture. A factor space is a one-dimensional (a line), two-dimensional (a

plane), three-dimensional (a tetrahedron) or any other imaginary space where mixture components interact. The boundary within which the mixture components interact is defined by the space. Scheffe stated that $(q - 1)$ space would be used to define the boundary where q components are interacting in a mixture. In other words, a mixture comprising of q components can be analyzed using a $(q - 1)$ dimensional space. For instance:

- a) For a mixture comprising two components i.e. $q = 2$ as in Figure 3.1, a line will be used to analyze the interaction between components. Thus, it is a one-dimensional space.

Figure 3.1: Two components in a one-dimensional space

- b) A mixture comprising three components, i.e. $q = 3$ as in Figure 3.2, a triangular simplex lattice is used in its analysis.

Figure 3.2: Three components in a two-dimensional space

- c) A mixture comprising of four components, i.e. $q = 4$ as in Figure 3.3, a tetrahedron simplex lattice is used in its analysis.

Figure 3.3: Four components in a three-dimensional space

3.3.1.2 Interaction of Components in Scheffe's Factor Space

The components of a mixture are always interacting with each other within the factor space. Three regions exist in the factor space. These regions are the vertices, borderlines, and the interior of the body space. Pure components of the mixture exist at the vertices of the factor spaces. The borderline can be a line for one-dimensional or two-dimensional factor space. It can also be both lines and plane for a three-dimensional, four-dimensional, etc. factor spaces. Two components of a mixture exist at any point on the plane border which depends on how many vertices that defined the plane border. All the component of a mixture exists right inside the body of the space. Also, at any point in the factor space, the total quantity of the Pseudo components must be equal to one. A two-dimensional factor space will be used to clarify the interaction of components. Figure 3.4 shows seven points on the two-dimensional factor space.

Figure 3.4: A two-dimensional factor space

The three points A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 are on the vertices. The three points A_{12} , A_{13} , and A_{23} are on the border of space. The remaining one A_{123} is right inside the body of the space.

A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 are called principal co-ordinates; only one pure component exists at any of these principal coordinates, and the total quantity of the Pseudo components of these coordinates is equal to one. The other components outside these coordinates are all zero. For instance, at coordinate A_1 , only A_1 exists and the quantity of its Pseudo component is equal to one. The other components are equal to zero.

A_{12} , A_{13} , and A_{23} are points or coordinates where binary mixtures occur; at these points only two components exist and the rest do not. For instance, at point A_{12} , components of A_1 and A_2 exist. The total quantity of Pseudo components of A_1 and A_2 at that point is equal to one, while the component A_3 is equal to zero at that point.

If A_{12} is midway, then the component of A_1 is equal to half and that of A_2 is equal to half, while A_3 is equal to zero at that point. At any point inside the space, all the three components A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 exist. The total quantity of the Pseudo component is still equal to one. Consequently, if a point A_{123} is exactly at the centroid of the space, the Pseudo component of A_1 is equal to those of A_3 and A_2 and is equal to one-third ($1/3$).

3.3.1.3 Five-Component Factor Space

This research work deals with a five-component sandcrete mixture. The components that form the sandcrete mixture are water/cement ratio, cement, periwinkle shell ash, fly ash, and sand. The number of components q is equal to five which is equal to four-dimensional factor space. A four-dimensional factor space is an imaginary dimension space. The imaginary space used is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: A four-dimensional factor space

Figure 3.5 shows 15 points on the four-dimensional factor space. The properties of the Pseudo components of the five-component mixture is shown in the Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Proportions of the Pseudo components

Points on factor space (A_{ijk})	Values of Pseudo components (K_{ijk})
A_1	(1, 0, 0, 0, 0)
A_2	(0, 1, 0, 0, 0)
A_3	(0, 0, 1, 0, 0)
A_4	(0, 0, 0, 1, 0)
A_5	(0, 0, 0, 0, 1)
A_{12}	(0.5, 0.5, 0, 0, 0)

A ₁₃	(0.5, 0, 0.5, 0, 0)
A ₁₄	(0.5, 0, 0, 0.5, 0)
A ₁₅	(0.5, 0, 0, 0, 0.5)
A ₂₃	(0, 0.5, 0.5, 0, 0)
A ₂₄	(0, 0.5, 0, 0.5, 0)
A ₂₅	(0, 0.5, 0, 0, 0.5)
A ₃₄	(0, 0, 0.5, 0.5, 0)
A ₃₅	(0, 0, 0.5, 0, 0.5)
A ₄₅	(0, 0, 0, 0.5, 0.5)

3.3.1.4 Relationship between Pseudo and Actual Components

In Scheffe’s mixture design, the Pseudo components have a relationship with the Actual components. This means that the Actual components can be derived from the Pseudo components and vice versa. According to Scheffe, Pseudo components are designated as X while the Actual components are designated as S. Hence the relationship between X and S as expressed by Scheffe is given in Equation (3.4).

$$S = A * X \tag{3.4}$$

Where A is the coefficient of the relationship. Equation (3.4) above can thus be transformed to:

$$X = A^{-1} * S \tag{3.5}$$

Let $A^{-1} = B$, hence Equation (3.5) becomes Equation (3.6)

$$X = B * S \tag{3.6}$$

The Equation (3.4) will be used to determine the Actual components of the mixture given that the Pseudo components are known, while Equations (3.5) and (3.6) will be used to determine the Pseudo components of the mixture when the Actual components are known. Since the five components are: Water, Cement, Periwinkle shell ash, Fly ash, and Sand,

Let S_1 = Water; S_2 = Cement; S_3 = Periwinkle shell ash; S_4 = Fly ash; and S_5 = Sand

Then, in keeping with the principle of absolute volume:

$$S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 + S_5 = S \quad (3.7)$$

Dividing Equation (3.7) through by S yields Equation (3.8)

$$\frac{S_1}{S} + \frac{S_2}{S} + \frac{S_3}{S} + \frac{S_4}{S} + \frac{S_5}{S} = 1 \quad (3.8)$$

Where $\frac{S_i}{S}$ is the proportion of the i^{th} component of the PSA-Fly ash cement mix.

$$\text{Let } \frac{S_i}{S} = Z_i \quad (\text{where } i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) \quad (3.9)$$

Substituting Equation (3.9) into Equation (3.8) gives Equation (3.10)

$$Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_3 + Z_4 + Z_5 = 1 \quad (3.10)$$

According to Scheffe's simplex lattice, the mix ratios when shown in an imaginary space will give 15 points on the four-dimensional factor space. Let the value of the Pseudo components of the mixture at a given point A_{ijk} , on the factor space, be K_{ijk} . In other words, the point A_{ijk} is an arbitrary point on the factor space and K_{ijk} is the arbitrary quantity of any of the Pseudo components. The proportion of the Pseudo components of the five-component mixture is given in Table 3.1. The starting set of Actual components, S and Pseudo components, X used in this research are shown in Table 3.2. The Actual components are the ingredients that make up the mix ratio of the sandcrete, and the values were gotten by mere gesticulation. Though randomly selected, the mix ratios were carefully chosen to be workable mixes having water/cement ratio ranging from 0.50 to 0.60. Since the selected mixes are all workable mixes, the other transformed ratios within the simplex are also workable.

Table 3.2 Actual and Pseudo Components

N	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4	S_5	Response	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5
1	0.58	0.98	0.01	0.01	6.00	Y_1	1	0	0	0	0
2	0.56	0.96	0.02	0.02	5.50	Y_2	0	1	0	0	0

3	0.54	0.92	0.05	0.03	5.00	Y ₃	0	0	1	0	0
4	0.52	0.95	0.04	0.01	4.50	Y ₄	0	0	0	1	0
5	0.50	0.95	0.03	0.02	4.00	Y ₅	0	0	0	0	1

where N = any point on the factor space

Y = response

Expanding Equation (3.4) gives Equation (3.11)

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ X_3 \\ X_4 \\ X_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.11)$$

Substituting the known values of Actual (S) and Pseudo (X) components, as given in Table 3.2, into Equation (3.11), and then solving the resulting equations:

For point N = 1

Substituting the known values in Table 3.2 into Equation (3.11) gives point N = 1

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.58 \\ 0.98 \\ 0.01 \\ 0.01 \\ 6.00 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.12)$$

Solving Equation (3.12), the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11} &= 0.58 \\ a_{21} &= 0.98 \\ a_{31} &= 0.01 \\ a_{41} &= 0.01 \\ a_{51} &= 6.00 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 2

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.56 \\ 0.96 \\ 0.02 \\ 0.02 \\ 5.50 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.13)$$

Solving Equation (3.13), the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{12} &= 0.56 \\ a_{22} &= 0.96 \\ a_{32} &= 0.02 \\ a_{42} &= 0.02 \\ a_{52} &= 5.50 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 3

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.54 \\ 0.92 \\ 0.05 \\ 0.03 \\ 5.00 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.14)$$

Solving Equation (3.14), the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{13} &= 0.54 \\ a_{23} &= 0.92 \\ a_{33} &= 0.05 \\ a_{43} &= 0.03 \\ a_{53} &= 5.00 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 4

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.52 \\ 0.95 \\ 0.04 \\ 0.01 \\ 4.50 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.15)$$

Solving Equation (3.15), the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{14} &= 0.52 \\ a_{24} &= 0.95 \\ a_{34} &= 0.04 \\ a_{44} &= 0.01 \\ a_{54} &= 4.50 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 5

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.50 \\ 0.95 \\ 0.03 \\ 0.02 \\ 4.00 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} & a_{15} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} & a_{25} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} & a_{35} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} & a_{45} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} & a_{54} & a_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.16)$$

Solving Equation (3.16), the following is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{15} &= 0.50 \\
 a_{25} &= 0.95 \\
 a_{35} &= 0.03 \\
 a_{45} &= 0.02 \\
 a_{55} &= 4.00
 \end{aligned}$$

Assembling the coefficients of matrix, A gives Equation (3.17)

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.17)$$

3.3.1.5 Determination of Actual Components of the Binary Mixture

The Actual components of the binary mixture (as represented by points N = 12 to N = 45) are determined by multiplying matrix [A] with values of matrix [X] expressed thus:

$$[S] = [A] * [X] \quad (3.18)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ X_3 \\ X_4 \\ X_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.19)$$

Substituting the known values of Pseudo components of the binary mixture, as given in Table 3.1, into Equation (3.19), and then solving the resulting equations:

For point N = 12

Substituting the values of Pseudo components at N = 12 into Equation (3.19):

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.20)$$

Solving Equation (3.20) gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_1 &= 0.57 \\
S_2 &= 0.97 \\
S_3 &= 0.015 \\
S_4 &= 0.015 \\
S_5 &= 5.75
\end{aligned}$$

For point N = 13

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.21)$$

Solving Equation (3.21) gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_1 &= 0.56 \\
S_2 &= 0.95 \\
S_3 &= 0.03 \\
S_4 &= 0.02 \\
S_5 &= 5.50
\end{aligned}$$

For point N = 14

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.22)$$

Solving Equation (3.22) gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_1 &= 0.55 \\
S_2 &= 0.965 \\
S_3 &= 0.025 \\
S_4 &= 0.01 \\
S_5 &= 5.25
\end{aligned}$$

For point N = 15

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.23)$$

Solving Equation (3.23) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.54 \\ S_2 &= 0.965 \\ S_3 &= 0.02 \\ S_4 &= 0.015 \\ S_5 &= 5.00 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 23

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.24)$$

Solving Equation (3.24) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.55 \\ S_2 &= 0.94 \\ S_3 &= 0.035 \\ S_4 &= 0.025 \\ S_5 &= 5.25 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 24

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

Solving Equation (3.25) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.54 \\ S_2 &= 0.955 \\ S_3 &= 0.03 \\ S_4 &= 0.015 \\ S_5 &= 5.00 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 25

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

Solving Equation (3.26) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.53 \\ S_2 &= 0.955 \\ S_3 &= 0.025 \\ S_4 &= 0.02 \\ S_5 &= 4.75 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 34

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.27)$$

Solving Equation (3.27) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.53 \\ S_2 &= 0.935 \\ S_3 &= 0.045 \\ S_4 &= 0.02 \\ S_5 &= 4.75 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 35

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.28)$$

Solving Equation (3.28) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.52 \\ S_2 &= 0.935 \\ S_3 &= 0.04 \\ S_4 &= 0.025 \\ S_5 &= 4.50 \end{aligned}$$

For point N = 45

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.58 & 0.56 & 0.54 & 0.52 & 0.50 \\ 0.98 & 0.96 & 0.92 & 0.95 & 0.95 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.03 \\ 0.01 & 0.02 & 0.03 & 0.01 & 0.02 \\ 6.00 & 5.50 & 5.00 & 4.50 & 4.00 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.29)$$

Solving Equation (3.29) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.51 \\ S_2 &= 0.95 \\ S_3 &= 0.035 \\ S_4 &= 0.015 \\ S_5 &= 4.25 \end{aligned}$$

Table 3.3 shows the Pseudo components and their corresponding Actual components at different points on the factor space.

Table 3.3: Values of Actual and Pseudo components for trial mixes

N	Values of Actual components					Response	Values of Pseudo components				
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅
1	0.58	0.98	0.01	0.01	6.00	Y ₁	1	0	0	0	0
2	0.56	0.96	0.02	0.02	5.50	Y ₂	0	1	0	0	0
3	0.54	0.92	0.05	0.03	5.00	Y ₃	0	0	1	0	0
4	0.52	0.95	0.04	0.01	4.50	Y ₄	0	0	0	1	0
5	0.50	0.95	0.03	0.02	4.00	Y ₅	0	0	0	0	1
12	0.57	0.97	0.015	0.015	5.75	Y ₁₂	0.5	0.5	0	0	0
13	0.56	0.95	0.03	0.02	5.50	Y ₁₃	0.5	0	0.5	0	0
14	0.55	0.965	0.025	0.01	5.25	Y ₁₄	0.5	0	0	0.5	0
15	0.54	0.965	0.02	0.015	5.00	Y ₁₅	0.5	0	0	0	0.5
23	0.55	0.94	0.035	0.025	5.25	Y ₂₃	0	0.5	0.5	0	0

24	0.54	0.955	0.03	0.015	5.00	Y_{24}	0	0.5	0	0.5	0
25	0.53	0.955	0.025	0.02	4.75	Y_{25}	0	0.5	0	0	0.5
34	0.53	0.935	0.045	0.02	4.75	Y_{34}	0	0	0.5	0.5	0
35	0.52	0.935	0.04	0.025	4.50	Y_{35}	0	0	0.5	0	0.5
45	0.51	0.95	0.035	0.015	4.25	Y_{45}	0	0	0	0.5	0.5

3.3.1.6 Responses

Responses, according to Simon (2003), refer to any measurable plastic or hardened properties of concrete (or sandcrete). These properties include compressive strength, flexural strength, elastic modulus, shear modulus etc. Cost can also be a response. The specified properties are called the responses or dependent variables, Y which are the performance criteria for optimizing the sandcrete. The performance criterion sought is the compressive strength of fly ash-PSA-cement sandcrete. The response is presented using a polynomial function of Pseudo components of the mixture.

Scheffe (1958) and Simon (2003) derived the equation of response to be:

$$Y = b_0 + \sum b_i X_i + \sum b_{ij} X_i X_j + \sum b_{ijk} X_i X_j X_k + \dots + e \quad (3.30)$$

where Y is the response; $b_0, b_i, b_{ij},$ and b_{ijk} are arbitrary constants; $X_i, X_j,$ and X_k are Pseudo components; and e is the random error term which represents the combined effects of all variables not included in the model.

3.3.1.7 Coefficients of the Polynomial

The number of coefficients of the polynomial depends on the number of components and the degree of polynomial the designer wants. Let the number of components be q , and the degree of polynomial be m . The least number of components, q in any given mixture is equal to 2. Hence, $2 \leq q \leq \infty$

For $q = 2$, m can be 1 or 2

For $q = 3$, m can be 1, 2, or 3

For $q = n$, m can be 1, 2, 3, ..., or n

Let the number of coefficients be K ;

According to Scheffe (2005),

$$K = \frac{(q + m - 1)!}{(q - 1)! m!} \quad (3.31)$$

For the five-component mixture used in this work, and selecting degree of polynomial of two, $q = 5$ while $m = 2$.

$$\text{Thus, } K = \frac{(5 + 2 - 1)!}{(5 - 1)! 2!} = 15$$

Therefore, the number of coefficients for the five-component mixture with two degrees of reaction is 15. This also determines the 15 different mix proportions used for the experiment.

The equation of response for the five-component mixture can be given as:

$$Y = b_0 + \sum b_i X_i + \sum b_{ij} X_i X_j + \sum b_{ii} X_i^2 + e \quad (3.32)$$

where $1 \leq i \leq j \leq 5$ with i and j representing points on the factor space.

Substituting the values of i and j into Equation (3.32) gives:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + b_{12} X_1 X_2 + b_{13} X_1 X_3 + b_{14} X_1 X_4 + b_{15} X_1 X_5 + b_{23} X_2 X_3 + b_{24} X_2 X_4 + b_{25} X_2 X_5 + b_{34} X_3 X_4 + b_{35} X_3 X_5 + b_{45} X_4 X_5 + b_{11} X_1^2 + b_{22} X_2^2 + b_{33} X_3^2 + b_{44} X_4^2 + b_{55} X_5^2 + e \quad (3.33)$$

Recall that Equation (3.2) states that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^q X_i = 1$$

$$\text{Hence, } \sum_{i=1}^5 X_i = 1 \quad (3.34)$$

This implies that:

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + X_5 = 1 \quad (3.35)$$

Multiplying Equation (3.35) by b_0 yields Equation (3.36)

$$b_0X_1 + b_0X_2 + b_0X_3 + b_0X_4 + b_0X_5 = b_0 \quad (3.36)$$

Multiplying Equation (3.35) by X_1 yields Equation (3.37)

$$X_1^2 + X_1X_2 + X_1X_3 + X_1X_4 + X_1X_5 = X_1 \quad (3.37)$$

Equation (3.37) can be transformed into Equation (3.38)

$$X_1^2 = X_1 - X_1X_2 - X_1X_3 - X_1X_4 - X_1X_5 \quad (3.38)$$

Similarly,

$$X_2^2 = X_2 - X_1X_2 - X_2X_3 - X_2X_4 - X_2X_5 \quad (3.39)$$

$$X_3^2 = X_3 - X_1X_3 - X_2X_3 - X_3X_4 - X_3X_5 \quad (3.40)$$

$$X_4^2 = X_4 - X_1X_4 - X_2X_4 - X_3X_4 - X_4X_5 \quad (3.41)$$

$$X_5^2 = X_5 - X_1X_5 - X_2X_5 - X_3X_5 - X_4X_5 \quad (3.42)$$

Substituting Equations (3.36), (3.38), (3.39), (3.40), (3.41), and (3.42) into Equation (3.33) yields Equation (3.43)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & b_0X_1 + b_0X_2 + b_0X_3 + b_0X_4 + b_0X_5 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + \\ & b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{14}X_1X_4 + b_{15}X_1X_5 + b_{23}X_2X_3 + b_{24}X_2X_4 + b_{25}X_2X_5 + \\ & b_{34}X_3X_4 + b_{35}X_3X_5 + b_{45}X_4X_5 + b_{11}X_1 - b_{11}X_1X_2 - b_{11}X_1X_3 - b_{11}X_1X_4 - \\ & b_{11}X_1X_5 + b_{22}X_2 - b_{22}X_1X_2 - b_{22}X_2X_3 - b_{22}X_2X_4 - b_{22}X_2X_5 + b_{33}X_3 - b_{33}X_1X_3 - \\ & b_{33}X_2X_3 - b_{33}X_3X_4 - b_{33}X_3X_5 + b_{44}X_4 - b_{44}X_1X_4 - b_{44}X_2X_4 - b_{44}X_3X_4 - b_{44}X_4X_5 + \\ & b_{55}X_5 - b_{55}X_1X_5 - b_{55}X_2X_5 - b_{55}X_3X_5 - b_{55}X_4X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

Collecting like terms, Equation (3.43) becomes Equation (3.44)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & X_1(b_0 + b_1 + b_{11}) + X_2(b_0 + b_2 + b_{22}) + X_3(b_0 + b_3 + b_{33}) + X_4(b_0 + b_4 + b_{44}) \\ & + X_5(b_0 + b_5 + b_{55}) + X_1X_2(b_{12} - b_{11} - b_{22}) + X_1X_3(b_{13} - b_{11} - b_{33}) \\ & + X_1X_4(b_{14} - b_{11} - b_{44}) + X_1X_5(b_{15} - b_{11} - b_{55}) \\ & + X_2X_3(b_{23} - b_{22} - b_{33}) + X_2X_4(b_{24} - b_{22} - b_{44}) \\ & + X_2X_5(b_{25} - b_{22} - b_{55}) + X_3X_4(b_{34} - b_{33} - b_{44}) \\ & + X_3X_5(b_{35} - b_{33} - b_{55}) + X_4X_5(b_{45} - b_{44} - b_{55}) + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.44)$$

Equation (3.44) can be expressed in the following form:

$$Y = \sum X_i(b_0 + b_i + b_{ii}) + \sum X_i X_j(b_{ij} - b_{ii} - b_{jj}) + e \quad (3.45)$$

Summing up the constant terms in Equation (3.45) gives Equation (3.46)

$$\alpha_i = b_0 + b_i + b_{ii} \quad (3.46)$$

$$\alpha_{ij} = b_{ij} - b_{ii} - b_{jj} \quad (3.47)$$

Substituting Equations (3.46) and (3.47) into Equation (3.45) yields Equation (3.48)

$$Y = \sum \alpha_i X_i + \sum \alpha_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (3.48)$$

From Equations (3.46) and (3.47), the constant terms can be written out as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= b_0 + b_1 + b_{11} \\ \alpha_2 &= b_0 + b_2 + b_{22} \\ \alpha_3 &= b_0 + b_3 + b_{33} \\ \alpha_4 &= b_0 + b_4 + b_{44} \\ \alpha_5 &= b_0 + b_5 + b_{55} \\ \alpha_{12} &= b_{12} - b_{11} - b_{22} \\ \alpha_{13} &= b_{13} - b_{11} - b_{33} \\ \alpha_{14} &= b_{14} - b_{11} - b_{44} \\ \alpha_{15} &= b_{15} - b_{11} - b_{55} \\ \alpha_{23} &= b_{23} - b_{22} - b_{33} \\ \alpha_{24} &= b_{24} - b_{22} - b_{44} \\ \alpha_{25} &= b_{25} - b_{22} - b_{55} \\ \alpha_{34} &= b_{34} - b_{33} - b_{44} \\ \alpha_{35} &= b_{35} - b_{33} - b_{55} \\ \alpha_{45} &= b_{45} - b_{44} - b_{55} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.49)$$

Substituting the values in Equation (3.49) into Equation (3.44) yields Equation (3.50)

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \alpha_3 X_3 + \alpha_4 X_4 + \alpha_5 X_5 + \alpha_{12} X_1 X_2 + \alpha_{13} X_1 X_3 + \alpha_{14} X_1 X_4 \\ &\quad + \alpha_{15} X_1 X_5 + \alpha_{23} X_2 X_3 + \alpha_{24} X_2 X_4 + \alpha_{25} X_2 X_5 + \alpha_{34} X_3 X_4 \\ &\quad + \alpha_{35} X_3 X_5 + \alpha_{45} X_4 X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.50)$$

$$\text{Let } Y = \ddot{Y} + e \quad (3.51)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{Y} = & \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \alpha_3 X_3 + \alpha_4 X_4 + \alpha_5 X_5 + \alpha_{12} X_1 X_2 + \alpha_{13} X_1 X_3 + \alpha_{14} X_1 X_4 \\ & + \alpha_{15} X_1 X_5 + \alpha_{23} X_2 X_3 + \alpha_{24} X_2 X_4 + \alpha_{25} X_2 X_5 + \alpha_{34} X_3 X_4 \\ & + \alpha_{35} X_3 X_5 + \alpha_{45} X_4 X_5\end{aligned}\quad (3.52a)$$

The Equation (3.52a) can be expressed in the form:

$$\ddot{Y} = \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i X_i + \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 5} \alpha_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (3.52b)$$

Equation (3.52b) is the response of the pure component, i and the binary component, ij . If the response function is represented by y , the response function for the pure components and that of the binary mixture components will be y_i and y_{ij} respectively.

$$y_i = \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i X_i \quad (3.53a)$$

$$y_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i X_i + \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 5} \alpha_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (3.53b)$$

If the response at i^{th} point on the factor space is y_i , then at point $N = 1$, component $X_1 = 1$ and components X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5 are all equal to zero. Then Equation (3.53a) becomes Equation (3.54)

$$y_1 = \alpha_1 \quad (3.54)$$

Similarly,

$$y_2 = \alpha_2 \quad (3.55)$$

$$y_3 = \alpha_3 \quad (3.56)$$

$$y_4 = \alpha_4 \quad (3.57)$$

$$y_5 = \alpha_5 \quad (3.58)$$

The Equations (3.54) to (3.58) can be expressed in the form:

$$y_i = \alpha_i \quad (3.59)$$

For point N = 12, i.e. the mid-point of the borderlines connecting points 1 and 2 of the factor space, component $X_1 = \frac{1}{2}$, $X_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, and $X_3 = X_4 = X_5 = 0$. The response at this point is y_{12} .

Then Equation (3.53b) becomes Equation (3.60a)

$$y_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 + \left(\alpha_{12} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (3.60a)$$

$$y_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{12} \quad (3.60b)$$

Similarly,

$$y_{13} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_3 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{13} \quad (3.61)$$

$$y_{14} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_4 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{14} \quad (3.62)$$

$$y_{15} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_5 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{15} \quad (3.63)$$

$$y_{23} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_3 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{23} \quad (3.64)$$

$$y_{24} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_4 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{24} \quad (3.65)$$

$$y_{25} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_5 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{25} \quad (3.66)$$

$$y_{34} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_3 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_4 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{34} \quad (3.67)$$

$$y_{35} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_3 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_5 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{35} \quad (3.68)$$

$$y_{45} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_4 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_5 + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{45} \quad (3.69)$$

Equations (3.60) to (3.69) can be written in the form:

$$y_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha_i + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_j + \frac{1}{4} \alpha_{ij} \quad (3.70)$$

Rearranging Equations (3.59) and (3.70) respectively give Equations (3.71) and (3.72)

$$\alpha_i = y_i \quad (3.71)$$

$$\alpha_{ij} = 4y_{ij} - 2\alpha_i - 2\alpha_j \quad (3.72)$$

If $\alpha_i = y_i$ and $\alpha_j = y_j$, then substituting into Equation (3.72) yields Equation (3.73)

$$\alpha_{ij} = 4y_{ij} - 2y_i - 2y_j \quad (3.73)$$

Substituting Equations (3.71) and (3.73) into Equation (3.50) yields Equation (3.74)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & y_1X_1 + y_2X_2 + y_3X_3 + y_4X_4 + y_5X_5 + (4y_{12} - 2y_1 - 2y_2)X_1X_2 + (4y_{13} - 2y_1 - \\ & 2y_3)X_1X_3 + (4y_{14} - 2y_1 - 2y_4)X_1X_4 + (4y_{15} - 2y_1 - 2y_5)X_1X_5 + (4y_{23} - 2y_2 - \\ & 2y_3)X_2X_3 + (4y_{24} - 2y_2 - 2y_4)X_2X_4 + (4y_{25} - 2y_2 - 2y_5)X_2X_5 + (4y_{34} - 2y_3 - \\ & 2y_4)X_3X_4 + (4y_{35} - 2y_3 - 2y_5)X_3X_5 + (4y_{45} - 2y_4 - 2y_5)X_4X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.74)$$

Expanding Equation (3.74) and rearranging gives Equation (3.75)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & y_1X_1 - 2y_1X_1X_2 - 2y_1X_1X_3 - 2y_1X_1X_4 - 2y_1X_1X_5 + y_2X_2 - 2y_2X_1X_2 - 2y_2X_2X_3 \\ & - 2y_2X_2X_4 - 2y_2X_2X_5 + y_3X_3 - 2y_3X_1X_3 - 2y_3X_2X_3 - 2y_3X_3X_4 - 2y_3X_3X_5 + y_4X_4 - \\ & 2y_4X_1X_4 - 2y_4X_2X_4 - 2y_4X_3X_4 - 2y_4X_4X_5 + y_5X_5 - 2y_5X_1X_5 - 2y_5X_2X_5 - 2y_5X_3X_5 \\ & - 2y_5X_4X_5 + 4y_{12}X_1X_2 + 4y_{13}X_1X_3 + 4y_{14}X_1X_4 + 4y_{15}X_1X_5 + 4y_{23}X_2X_3 + 4y_{24}X_2X_4 + \\ & 4y_{25}X_2X_5 + 4y_{34}X_3X_4 + 4y_{35}X_3X_5 + 4y_{45}X_4X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.75)$$

Factorizing Equation (3.75) gives Equation (3.76)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & y_1X_1(1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_4 - 2X_5) + y_2X_2(1 - 2X_1 - 2X_3 - 2X_4 - 2X_5) + \\ & y_3X_3(1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_4 - 2X_5) + y_4X_4(1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_5) + \\ & y_5X_5(1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_4) + 4y_{12}X_1X_2 + 4y_{13}X_1X_3 + 4y_{14}X_1X_4 + 4y_{15}X_1X_5 + \\ & 4y_{23}X_2X_3 + 4y_{24}X_2X_4 + 4y_{25}X_2X_5 + 4y_{34}X_3X_4 + 4y_{35}X_3X_5 + 4y_{45}X_4X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.76)$$

Recall that Equation (3.35) states that:

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + X_5 = 1$$

Multiplying Equation (3.35) by 2 gives Equation (3.77)

$$2X_1 + 2X_2 + 2X_3 + 2X_4 + 2X_5 = 2 \quad (3.77)$$

Subtracting 1 from both sides of Equation (3.77) gives Equation (3.78)

$$2X_1 + 2X_2 + 2X_3 + 2X_4 + 2X_5 - 1 = 1 \quad (3.78)$$

Equation (3.78) can be expressed as:

$$2X_1 - 1 = 1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_4 - 2X_5 \quad (3.79)$$

Similarly,

$$2X_2 - 1 = 1 - 2X_1 - 2X_3 - 2X_4 - 2X_5 \quad (3.80)$$

$$2X_3 - 1 = 1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_4 - 2X_5 \quad (3.81)$$

$$2X_4 - 1 = 1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_5 \quad (3.82)$$

$$2X_5 - 1 = 1 - 2X_1 - 2X_2 - 2X_3 - 2X_4 \quad (3.83)$$

Substituting Equations (3.79) to (3.83) into Equation (3.76) yields Equation (3.84)

$$\begin{aligned} Y = & X_1(2X_1 - 1)y_1 + X_2(2X_2 - 1)y_2 + X_3(2X_3 - 1)y_3 + X_4(2X_4 - 1)y_4 + X_5(2X_5 - 1)y_5 \\ & + 4y_{12}X_1X_2 + 4y_{13}X_1X_3 + 4y_{14}X_1X_4 + 4y_{15}X_1X_5 + 4y_{23}X_2X_3 + 4y_{24}X_2X_4 \\ & + 4y_{25}X_2X_5 + 4y_{34}X_3X_4 + 4y_{35}X_3X_5 + 4y_{45}X_4X_5 + e \end{aligned} \quad (3.84)$$

Equation (3.84) is the mixture design model for the optimization of a sandcrete mixture consisting of five components. The terms y_i and y_{ij} represent the compressive strength at the point i and ij respectively. These responses are determined by carrying out laboratory tests.

3.3.1.8 Control Points

Another set of fifteen mix proportions are required to confirm the adequacy of the model of Equation (3.84). The set of mixture proportions are called Control Mixture Proportions. Therefore, fifteen control points will be used. They are $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5, C_{12}, C_{13}, C_{14}, C_{15}, C_{23}, C_{24}, C_{25}, C_{34}, C_{35},$ and C_{45} . The Actual and Pseudo components of the control points are shown in the table below. The values given in Table 3.4 were gotten by mere gesticulation and randomization.

Table 3.4: Values of Actual and Pseudo components for control mixes

C	Values of Actual components					Response	Values of Pseudo components				
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅
1	0.54	0.94	0.035	0.025	5.15	YC ₁	0.45	0.25	0.3	0	0
2	0.57	0.94	0.04	0.02	5.00	YC ₂	0.4	0	0.2	0.4	0
3	0.52	0.96	0.025	0.015	5.10	YC ₃	0.35	0	0	0.3	0.35
4	0.56	0.97	0.02	0.01	5.25	YC ₄	0.2	0.45	0	0	0.35
5	0.55	0.955	0.03	0.015	5.05	YC ₅	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	0
12	0.50	0.96	0.03	0.01	5.20	YC ₁₂	0.2	0	0.2	0.4	0.2
13	0.58	0.92	0.05	0.03	5.00	YC ₁₃	0	0.3	0.3	0.15	0.25
14	0.53	0.945	0.04	0.015	5.35	YC ₁₄	0.35	0.25	0.2	0.2	0
15	0.57	0.955	0.02	0.025	5.30	YC ₁₅	0.25	0.25	0.35	0.15	0
23	0.51	0.97	0.01	0.02	5.25	YC ₂₃	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
24	0.54	0.96	0.02	0.02	5.40	YC ₂₄	0.25	0.15	0.35	0.15	0.1
25	0.52	0.955	0.015	0.03	5.20	YC ₂₅	0.15	0.2	0.35	0.1	0.2
34	0.55	0.96	0.03	0.01	5.45	YC ₃₄	0.1	0.15	0.3	0.25	0.2
35	0.50	0.955	0.02	0.025	5.15	YC ₃₅	0.25	0.25	0	0.25	0.25
45	0.56	0.955	0.03	0.015	5.50	YC ₄₅	0.15	0.35	0.15	0	0.35

3.3.2 Proportioning/Batching of the Sandcrete Materials

This entails determining the quantity by mass of each ingredient in the sandcrete mix. All the materials were weighed using the weighing balance. From Scheffe's optimization model, thirty mix proportions were obtained; fifteen for trial mix and another fifteen for control mix. Three sandcrete blocks each were cast from each mix ratio making a total of ninety blocks. The expected

mass of sandcrete block was obtained by simply multiplying the expected volume of sandcrete block by the approximate density value of sandcrete (known to be $1900\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$). This is expressed mathematically as in Equation (3.85):

$$\text{Mass of sandcrete block} = \text{volume of sandcrete block} \times \text{density of sandcrete} \quad (3.85)$$

For the purpose of this research work, a mould of $450\text{mm} \times 125\text{mm} \times 225\text{mm}$ was used. Therefore,

$$\text{Volume of sandcrete block} = (450 \times 125 \times 225)\text{mm}^3 = 12656250\text{mm}^3 = 0.0127\text{m}^3$$

Applying Equation (3.85),

$$\text{Mass of sandcrete block} = 0.0127 \times 1900 = 24.13\text{kg} = 24130\text{g}$$

Therefore, the mass of individual ingredients of each mix ratio can now be calculated. As an illustration, from Table 3.3 (i.e. trial mixes) and for mix N_1 ; $S_1 = 0.58$, $S_2 = 0.98$, $S_3 = 0.01$, $S_4 = 0.01$, and $S_5 = 6.00$. Recall that Equation (3.7) states that:

$$S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 + S_5 = S$$

$$\text{Consequently, } S = 0.58 + 0.98 + 0.01 + 0.01 + 6.00 = 7.58$$

$$\text{Hence, mass of water} = \frac{S_1}{S} \times 24130 = \frac{0.58}{7.58} \times 24130 = 1846.36\text{g}$$

$$\text{mass of cement} = \frac{S_2}{S} \times 24130 = \frac{0.98}{7.58} \times 24130 = 3119.71\text{g}$$

$$\text{mass of PSA} = \frac{S_3}{S} \times 24130 = \frac{0.01}{7.58} \times 24130 = 31.83\text{g}$$

$$\text{mass of fly ash} = \frac{S_4}{S} \times 24130 = \frac{0.01}{7.58} \times 24130 = 31.83\text{g}$$

$$\text{mass of sand} = \frac{S_5}{S} \times 24130 = \frac{6.00}{7.58} \times 24130 = 19100.26\text{g}$$

The same procedure was applied in determining the mass of the individual ingredients making up every other mix ratio represented in Tables 3.3 and 3.4. In this regard, the masses of the constituent ingredients of sandcrete for both trial and control mixes are as shown in Tables 3.5 and 3.6 respectively.

Table 3.5: Mass of constituents of sandcrete for trial mixes (*g*)

N	Water	Cement	PSA	Fly ash	Sand
1	1846.36	3119.71	31.83	31.83	19100.26
2	1913.99	3281.13	68.36	68.36	18798.16
3	1992.39	3394.43	184.48	110.69	18448.01
4	2084.32	3807.89	160.33	40.08	18037.38
5	2193.64	4167.91	131.62	87.75	17549.09
12	1878.98	3197.55	49.45	49.45	18954.58
13	1913.99	3246.95	102.54	68.36	18798.16
14	1951.69	3424.33	88.71	35.49	18629.78
15	1992.39	3560.47	73.79	55.34	18448.01
23	1951.69	3335.62	124.20	88.71	18629.78
24	1992.39	3523.57	110.69	55.34	18448.01
25	2036.45	3669.45	96.06	76.85	18251.19
34	2036.45	3592.60	172.91	76.85	18251.19
35	2084.32	3747.77	160.33	100.21	18037.38
45	2136.51	3979.77	146.62	62.84	17804.25

Table 3.6: Mass of constituents of sandcrete for control mixes (*g*)

C	Water	Cement	PSA	Fly ash	Sand
1	1947.71	3390.46	126.24	90.17	18575.41
2	2093.47	3452.39	146.91	73.46	18363.77
3	1895.41	3499.21	91.13	54.68	18589.58
4	1984.26	3437.02	70.87	35.43	18602.42
5	2010.83	3491.54	109.68	54.84	18463.11
12	1800.75	3457.43	108.04	36.01	18727.76
13	2126.96	3373.80	183.36	110.02	18335.87
14	1858.85	3314.37	140.29	52.61	18763.88
15	2002.05	3354.32	70.25	87.81	18615.57
23	1820.46	3462.44	35.70	71.39	18740.01
24	1877.55	3337.87	69.54	69.54	18775.50
25	1867.20	3429.19	53.86	107.72	18672.02
34	1895.93	3309.26	103.41	34.47	18786.93
35	1814.29	3465.29	72.57	90.71	18687.14
45	1913.99	3264.04	102.54	51.27	18798.16

3.4 ERROR OF REPLICATES

Errors exist in the experimental test due to human inconsistency, variation in test tools and equipment, temperature, pressure and the likes. These are described as random error. For each arbitrary point of observation, replicate values are obtained which are used to determine the mean value of the response at such points. Due to the inconsistencies aforementioned, the replicate values vary, therefore the mean value is used. The replicate variance at arbitrary points of observation is designated as S_i^2 . Cramer (1946) gave the Equation of variance as:

$$S_y^2 = \frac{1}{(n-1)} \times [\sum (y_i - y)^2] \quad \text{with } 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (3.86)$$

where n is the number of observations, y_i is the value at any arbitrary point of observation, and y is the mean value of the y_i values. That is:

$$y = \frac{\sum y_i}{n} \quad \text{with } 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (3.87)$$

When Equation (3.87) is expanded, it approximately becomes Equation (3.88)

$$S_y^2 = \frac{1}{(n-1)} \times \left[\sum y_i^2 - \frac{(\sum y_i)^2}{n} \right] \quad (3.88)$$

Thus the equation of variance of the replicates at any arbitrary points of observation will be given as in Equation (3.89)

$$S_i^2 = \frac{1}{(n_i-1)} \times \left[\sum y_i^2 - \frac{(\sum y_i)^2}{n_i} \right] \quad (3.89)$$

Hence the variance of the replicates at all points of observation will be the summarization of the individual variances divided by the number of observation points.

$$S_y^2 = \frac{1}{V} \times \sum S_i^2 \quad (3.90)$$

V is the degree of freedom which is equal to $n - 1$, therefore the random error or standard deviation becomes Equation (3.91)

$$S_y = \sqrt{(S_y^2)} \quad (3.91)$$

3.5 TESTING THE FIT OF THE MODELS

The practice of science involves formulating and testing hypotheses and assertions that are capable of being proven false using a test of observed data. In scientific and medical research, null hypotheses a major role in testing the significance of differential treatment and control groups. The derived models and actual experimental observations are tested using statistical tools. To do this,

it is prudent to state the statistical hypothesis used. A hypothesis of the form “there is no difference between A and B” is the basis for statistical tests of significance.

Null hypothesis in a statistical test is the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between specified populations; any observed difference being due to sampling or experimental error. It corresponds to a general or default position. The null hypothesis can never be proven; a set of data can only reject a null hypothesis or fail to reject it. For example, if the comparison of two groups reveal statistically no significant difference between the two, it does not mean that there is no difference in reality but only means that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Null hypothesis is typically paired with a second hypothesis called Alternative hypothesis which asserts a particular relationship between the phenomena.

Let the Null Hypothesis be denoted with H_0 and the Alternative Hypothesis with H_a . For this work,

Null hypothesis H_0 : there is no significant difference between the experimental and theoretical expected results.

Alternative hypothesis H_a : there is a significant difference between the experimental and theoretical expected results.

These hypotheses are tested at a specified significance level α . The level of significance for a statistical test of hypothesis represents the maximum tolerable risk of incorrectly rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 . The significance level used for testing the model in this work was 5%.

Such tests used to check significance levels of difference between data include t-test, F-test, Z-statistics and X^2 -statistics. In the t-test, A and B are mean values. In the F-test, A and B are variances (squares of standard deviation). These hypotheses were tested for the model using Student t-test.

Student t-Test Method

This method assumes that the results follow the normal distribution if the null hypothesis is true, which usually stipulates that there is no significant difference between the means of the two data sets. It is best used to try and determine whether there is a difference between two independent sample groups. For the test to be applicable, the sample groups must be completely independent and it is best used when the sample size is too small to use more advanced methods.

Akhnazorova (1982) observed that experiments involving simplex design are “saturated” in that they have no degree of freedom. As a result, additional points of observation are required to test the adequacy of the model. In his explanation, the variance, S_y^2 of the predicted response is as a result of error accumulation. He further explained that the variance S_t^2 is similar at all points of observation and the replicate values are the average of α_i and α_{ij} replicate observations. He gave the equation of the estimated variance as in Equation (3.92):

$$S^2 = S_y^2 \left[\left(\sum \frac{a_i^2}{n_i} \right) + \left(\sum \frac{a_{ij}^2}{n_{ij}} \right) \right] \quad \text{with } 1 \leq i \leq q \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq j \leq q \text{ respectively} \quad (3.92)$$

In this work, the number of replicates is the same i.e. $n_i = n_{ij} = n$

Thus the Equation (3.92) will be written as expressed in Equation (3.93)

$$S^2 = S_y^2 \left[\left(\sum \frac{a_i^2}{n} \right) + \left(\sum \frac{a_{ij}^2}{n} \right) \right] \quad (3.93)$$

Further simplification of Equation (3.93) gives Equation (3.94)

$$S^2 = \frac{S_y^2}{n} \times \left(\sum a_i^2 + \sum a_{ij}^2 \right) \quad (3.94)$$

$$\text{Taking } \Sigma = \left(\sum a_i^2 + \sum a_{ij}^2 \right) \quad (3.95)$$

Equation (3.94) simplifies to Equation (3.96)

$$S^2 = S_y^2 \times \frac{\Sigma}{n} \quad (3.96)$$

$$\text{In a nutshell, } Y = \left(\sum a_i \right) n_i + \left(\sum a_{ij} \right) n_{ij} + e \quad (3.97)$$

3.6 DEVELOPMENT OF COMPUTER PROGRAM

Computer program was developed for the Scheffe’s simplex model for prediction of compressive strength of cement blended Fly Ash-Periwinkle Shell Ash sandcrete block using Visual Basic 6.0. The program is user-friendly and can be used to predict the compressive strength of the blocks if the mix ratio is known or vice versa. The computer program is presented in Appendix II.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

The results obtained from the tests performed in this research work are presented in this chapter.

The tests performed include:

- i. Sieve analyses of fly ash and PSA
- ii. Chemical (pozzolanicity) tests on fly ash and PSA
- iii. Slump test
- iv. Compressive strength test

4.1.1 Sieve Analyses of fly ash and PSA

Dry method of sieving was employed with a total mass of 1000g of fly ash and 1500g of PSA sieved. The following calculations were done with respect to the sieve analyses:

$$\text{Mass of sample retained, } M_n = \text{Mass of [sieve + dry sample]} - \text{Mass of empty sieve} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{Cumulative mass of sample retained} = \sum_{i=1}^n M_n \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{Percentage of sample retained, } \%R_n = \frac{\text{Mass of sample retained}}{\text{Total mass of sample sieved, } w} \times 100 \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{Cumulative percentage of sample retained} = \sum_{i=1}^n R_n \quad (4.4)$$

$$\text{Percentage of sample passing, } \%P_n = 100 - \sum_{i=1}^n R_n \quad (4.5)$$

The coefficient of uniformity, C_u and the coefficient of curvature, C_c are expressed mathematically in Equations (4.6) and (4.7) respectively.

$$C_u = \frac{D_{60}}{D_{10}} \quad (4.6)$$

$$Cc = \frac{D_{30}^2}{D_{10} \times D_{60}} \quad (4.7)$$

where D_{10} = sieve size at 10% of sample passing

D_{30} = sieve size at 30% of sample passing

D_{60} = sieve size at 60% of sample passing

The results obtained from the sieve analyses are tabulated in Tables 4.1a and 4.1b. The corresponding gradation curves for both fly ash and PSA are presented in Figures 4.1 and 4.2 respectively.

Table 4.1a: Sieve analysis of fly ash

Sieve size (mm)	Mass of empty sieve (g)	Mass of [sieve + dry sample] (g)	Mass of sample retained (g)	Cumulative mass of sample retained (g)	% of sample retained	Cumulative % of sample retained	% of sample passing
1.180	398.21	413.85	15.64	15.64	1.56	1.56	98.44
0.600	372.63	398.47	25.84	41.48	2.58	4.14	95.86
0.425	345.72	381.20	35.48	76.96	3.55	7.69	92.31
0.300	318.27	364.32	46.05	123.01	4.61	12.30	87.70
0.212	306.46	414.27	107.81	230.82	10.78	23.08	76.92
0.150	298.38	609.00	310.62	541.44	31.06	54.14	45.86
Pan	273.02	728.65	455.63	997.07	45.56	99.70	0.30
TOTAL			$w_1=997.07$		99.70		

$$\text{Mass loss during sieve analysis} = \frac{w - w_1}{w} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{1000 - 997.07}{1000} \times 100 = 0.293\%$$

Figure 4.1: Gradation curve for fly ash

$$Cu = \frac{D_{60}}{D_{10}} = \frac{0.17}{0.11} = 1.55$$

$$Cc = \frac{D_{30}^2}{D_{10} \times D_{60}} = \frac{0.14^2}{0.11 \times 0.17} = 1.05$$

Table 4.1b: Sieve analysis of periwinkle shell ash

Sieve size (mm)	Mass of empty sieve (g)	Mass of [sieve + dry sample] (g)	Mass of sample retained (g)	Cumulative mass of sample retained (g)	% of sample retained	Cumulative % of sample retained	% of sample passing
1.180	398.21	426.86	28.65	28.65	1.91	1.91	98.09
0.600	372.63	451.08	78.45	107.10	5.23	7.14	92.86
0.425	345.72	457.96	112.24	219.34	7.48	14.62	85.38
0.300	318.27	610.99	292.72	512.06	19.51	34.13	65.87
0.212	306.46	709.02	402.56	914.62	26.84	60.97	39.03
0.150	298.38	634.56	336.18	1250.80	22.41	83.38	16.62

Pan	273.02	521.15	248.13	1498.93	16.54	99.92	0.08
TOTAL			$w_1=1498.93$		99.92		

$$\text{Mass loss during sieve analysis} = \frac{w - w_1}{w} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{1500 - 1498.93}{1500} \times 100 = 0.0713\%$$

Figure 4.2: Gradation curve for PSA

$$Cu = \frac{D_{60}}{D_{10}} = \frac{0.28}{0.14} = 2$$

$$Cc = \frac{D_{30}^2}{D_{10} \times D_{60}} = \frac{0.2^2}{0.14 \times 0.28} = 1.02$$

4.1.2 Chemical (pozzolanicity) tests on fly ash and PSA

The chemical analysis on fly ash and periwinkle shell ash produced the results tabulated in Table 4.2a and Table 4.2b respectively.

Table 4.2a: Chemical properties of fly ash

Chemical composition	Percentage by weight
SiO ₂	54.2
Al ₂ O ₃	20.46
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.88
CaO	8.72
K ₂ O	0.78
Na ₂ O	0.32
MgO	2.68
SO ₃	1.77
Loss on ignition	6.43

Table 4.2b: Chemical properties of periwinkle shell ash

Chemical composition	Percentage by weight
SiO ₂	33.72
Al ₂ O ₃	10.42
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.08
CaO	40.46
K ₂ O	0.64
Na ₂ O	0.28
MgO	0.12
SO ₃	0.22
Loss on ignition	7.08

4.1.3 Slump test

The slump test, which was carried out at a slump time of 10 seconds for each observation point, was necessary to determine the workability of the mixes used for this research work. The results of the experiment performed on both the trial and control mixes are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Slump of fly ash-PSA sandcrete

Observation points	Slump (cm)
N ₁	2.4
N ₂	1.5
N ₃	1.8
N ₄	3.7
N ₅	2.8
N ₁₂	1.9
N ₁₃	1.1
N ₁₄	2.6
N ₁₅	4.2
N ₂₃	1.6
N ₂₄	1.4
N ₂₅	2.1
N ₃₄	3.4
N ₃₅	2.5
N ₄₅	1.9
C ₁	3.7
C ₂	2.2
C ₃	1.0
C ₄	4.1
C ₅	2.3
C ₁₂	3.3

C ₁₃	1.9
C ₁₄	2.0
C ₁₅	2.9
C ₂₃	2.6
C ₂₄	3.0
C ₂₅	1.7
C ₃₄	2.8
C ₃₅	2.4
C ₄₅	1.4

4.1.4 Compressive strength test

This test was conducted on the cast sandcrete blocks to determine the compressive strength of each replicate specimen after 28 days of curing. The mass of each block was obtained using a weighing balance, and the values are shown on Tables 4.4a and 4.4b for trial and control mixes respectively. The density of the blocks was then calculated having obtained the mass using Equation (4.8).

$$\text{Density of block (in kg/m}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Mass of block}}{\text{Volume of block}} \quad (4.8)$$

where $\text{Volume of block (m}^3\text{)} = (0.45 \times 0.125 \times 0.225)\text{m}^3 = 0.0127\text{m}^3$

The density values are presented on Tables 4.5a and 4.5b. The Universal Testing Machine gave compressive load values which are tabulated on Tables 4.6a and 4.6b. The compressive strength of each replicate block was calculated using Equation (4.9).

$$\text{Compressive strength } f_c = \frac{F}{A} \quad (4.9)$$

where $f_c = \text{compressive strength (N/mm}^2\text{)}$

$F = \text{crushing load (N)}$

$A = \text{contact area of specimen(mm}^2\text{)} = (450 \times 125)\text{mm}^2 = 56250\text{mm}^2$

The compressive strength values are shown on Tables 4.7a and 4.7b.

Table 4.4a: Mass of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks for trial mixes

Observation points N	Mass (kg)			Average mass (kg)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	23.2	22.6	23.4	23.07
2	23.6	23.4	23.4	23.47
3	23.6	23.6	23.4	23.53
4	23.0	23.2	23.6	23.27
5	23.6	25.0	24.6	24.40
12	23.8	22.6	23.4	23.27
13	23.2	23.6	25.0	23.93
14	23.2	23.6	23.8	23.53
15	23.6	22.6	23.8	23.33
23	24.0	23.6	23.8	23.80
24	23.6	24.0	24.4	24.00
25	23.6	22.8	23.6	23.33
34	23.2	23.2	23.6	23.33
35	22.2	23.6	24.0	23.27
45	24.6	23.0	24.2	23.93

Table 4.4b: Mass of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks for control mixes

Observation points C	Mass (kg)			Average mass (kg)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	24.2	24.8	23.4	24.13
2	24.6	24.0	24.0	24.20
3	24.8	24.0	24.6	24.47
4	25.2	24.2	25.0	24.80
5	23.2	23.6	23.8	23.53
12	22.8	23.8	23.0	23.20
13	22.8	23.6	23.6	23.33
14	23.6	23.2	22.4	23.07
15	23.8	23.6	24.2	23.87
23	23.6	23.4	23.6	23.53
24	24.2	24.2	24.4	24.27
25	25.2	24.6	24.8	24.87
34	22.8	23.2	23.4	23.13
35	23.8	24.2	24.8	24.27
45	24.8	24.4	24.4	24.53

Table 4.5a: Density of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks for trial mixes

Observation points N	Density (kg/m ³)			Average density (kg/m ³)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	1826.77	1779.53	1842.52	1816.27
2	1858.27	1842.52	1842.52	1847.77
3	1858.27	1858.27	1842.52	1853.02
4	1811.02	1826.77	1858.27	1832.02
5	1858.27	1968.50	1937.01	1921.26
12	1874.02	1779.53	1842.52	1832.02
13	1826.77	1858.27	1968.50	1884.51
14	1826.77	1858.27	1874.02	1853.02
15	1858.27	1779.53	1874.02	1837.27
23	1889.76	1858.27	1874.02	1874.02
24	1858.27	1889.76	1921.26	1889.76
25	1858.27	1795.28	1858.27	1837.27
34	1826.77	1826.77	1858.27	1837.27
35	1748.03	1858.27	1889.76	1832.02
45	1937.01	1811.02	1905.51	1884.51

Table 4.5b: Density of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks for control mixes

Observation points C	Density (kg/m ³)			Average density (kg/m ³)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	1905.51	1952.76	1842.52	1900.26
2	1937.01	1889.76	1889.76	1905.51
3	1952.76	1889.76	1937.01	1926.51
4	1984.25	1905.51	1968.50	1952.75
5	1826.77	1858.27	1874.02	1853.02
12	1795.28	1874.02	1811.02	1826.77
13	1795.28	1858.27	1858.27	1837.27
14	1858.27	1826.77	1763.78	1816.27
15	1874.02	1858.27	1905.51	1879.27
23	1858.27	1842.52	1858.27	1853.02
24	1905.51	1905.51	1921.26	1910.76
25	1984.25	1937.01	1952.76	1958.01
34	1795.28	1826.77	1842.52	1821.52
35	1874.02	1905.51	1952.76	1910.76
45	1952.76	1921.26	1921.26	1931.76

Table 4.6a: Compressive load of fly ash-PSA sandcrete for trial mixes

Observation points N	Compressive Load (KN)			Average compressive load (KN)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	110	94	110	104.67
2	182	170	170	174
3	154	150	144	149.33
4	184	192	200	192
5	200	216	216	210.67
12	168	148	162	159.33
13	154	154	166	158
14	154	164	170	162.67
15	148	136	152	145.33
23	218	200	212	210
24	166	174	174	171.33
25	162	156	164	160.67
34	150	146	168	154.67
35	184	196	202	194
45	204	186	198	196

Table 4.6b: Compressive load of fly ash-PSA sandcrete for control mixes

Observation points C	Compressive Load (KN)			Average compressive load (KN)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	256	264	232	250.67
2	192	180	180	184
3	274	250	266	263.33
4	150	126	138	138
5	158	164	170	164
12	174	186	174	178
13	144	154	150	149.33
14	152	146	134	144
15	258	254	270	260.67
23	202	198	202	200.67
24	202	206	208	205.33
25	228	212	220	220
34	184	190	196	190
35	220	226	234	226.67
45	220	212	210	214

Table 4.7a: Compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete for trial mixes

Observation points N	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)			Average compressive strength (N/mm ²)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	1.96	1.67	1.96	1.86
2	3.24	3.02	3.02	3.09
3	2.74	2.67	2.56	2.66
4	3.27	3.41	3.56	3.41
5	3.56	3.84	3.84	3.75
12	2.99	2.63	2.88	2.83
13	2.74	2.74	2.95	2.81
14	2.74	2.92	3.02	2.89
15	2.63	2.42	2.70	2.58
23	3.88	3.56	3.77	3.74
24	2.95	3.09	3.09	3.04
25	2.88	2.77	2.92	2.86
34	2.67	2.60	2.99	2.75
35	3.27	3.48	3.59	3.45
45	3.63	3.31	3.52	3.49

Table 4.7b: Compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete for control mixes

Observation points C	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)			Average compressive strength (N/mm ²)
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	
1	4.55	4.69	4.12	4.45
2	3.41	3.20	3.20	3.27
3	4.87	4.44	4.73	4.68
4	2.67	2.24	2.45	2.45
5	2.81	2.92	3.02	2.92
12	3.09	3.31	3.09	3.16
13	2.56	2.74	2.67	2.66
14	2.70	2.60	2.38	2.56
15	4.59	4.52	4.80	4.64
23	3.59	3.52	3.59	3.57
24	3.59	3.66	3.70	3.65
25	4.05	3.77	3.91	3.91
34	3.27	3.38	3.48	3.38
35	3.91	4.02	4.16	4.03
45	3.91	3.77	3.73	3.80

4.2 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results obtained from this research work are discussed in this section.

- i. Both fly ash and PSA were characterized to have good cementitious properties/compositions by meeting standard requirements after sieve analysis and pozzolanicity tests were conducted. The values obtained from the estimation of coefficient of uniformity and coefficient of curvature show that both the fly ash and the PSA are well graded and offer workable mixes for better sandcrete strength. Also, the results obtained from pozzolanicity test show that the fly ash met the ASTM C618 requirement, which prescribes that a pozzolan should contain $\text{SiO}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \geq 70\% \text{wt}$. The PSA did not meet this requirement but met that of BS EN 197-1 (2009) which stipulates 25% silica content for a pozzolan to be considered to have cementitious composition. The PSA proved to be a high lime pozzolan due to its high calcium oxides and silica oxides content, hence the ash can act like mineral cementitious materials though may not be as reactive as cement.
- ii. Compressive strength test was carried out to determine the compressive strength of the cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks. Slump test was conducted on each mix and the results obtained suggest that the mix ratios used have good workability. The compressive load of each moulded block was determined as well as the mass and density. The highest average compressive strength value of sandcrete for trial was found to be 3.75 N/mm^2 while that of control was 4.68 N/mm^2 . The results show that the fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks tested have compressive strength property within the range for sandcrete blocks.
- iii. Mathematical model was formulated which was used to predict the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks.
- iv. The experimental compressive strength and model-predicted compressive strength were compared and the maximum percentage difference between both was found to be 15.41%.
- v. The model developed was tested for adequacy using statistical Student t-Test at 95% confidence level. It was observed that there was no significant difference between the experimental values and those obtained from the model thereby inferring a null hypothesis.
- vi. Scheffe's simplex model was used to develop a computer program. The computer program developed using Visual Basic 6.0 can predict all possible combinations of mix proportions

of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks given the compressive strength, and can also predict the compressive strength given a mix ratio.

- vii. The optimum compressive strength value obtained from the executed computer program was 3.9175 N/mm². The corresponding mix ratio for the optimum compressive strength is Water = 0.675, Cement = 1.19, PSA = 0.0375, Fly ash = 0.0225, Sand = 6.25.

4.3 FORMULATION OF THE MODELS OF OPTIMIZATION

The compressive strength (i.e. the responses) developed after 28 days for each observation point is affected by the mix proportion at that point. These responses obtained from the experimental investigation were used to formulate Scheffe's simplex model. This model was used to develop a computer program for the optimization of compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete.

The final Scheffe's simplex model for the determination of compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete was formulated by substituting the values of the compressive strength results y_i from Tables 4.7a and 4.7b into Scheffe's model given in Equation (3.84). Substituting these values gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y = & 1.86X_1(2X_1 - 1) + 3.09X_2(2X_2 - 1) + 2.66X_3(2X_3 - 1) + 3.41X_4(2X_4 - 1) \\
 & + 3.75X_5(2X_5 - 1) + 11.32X_1X_2 + 11.24X_1X_3 + 11.56X_1X_4 + 10.32X_1X_5 \\
 & + 14.96X_2X_3 + 12.16X_2X_4 + 11.44X_2X_5 + 11X_3X_4 + 13.8X_3X_5 \\
 & + 13.96X_4X_5
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

Equation (4.10) is the Scheffe's model for optimization of compressive strength of fly ash-PSA sandcrete. The compressive strengths from the Scheffe's response function were calculated using Equation (4.10). The experimental result values and that obtained from Scheffe's model are as shown in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: Values of compressive strength obtained from Scheffe's Response Function

Observation points	Experimental compressive strength (N/mm ²)	Scheffe's model compressive strength (N/mm ²)
N ₁	1.86	1.86
N ₂	3.09	3.09

N ₃	2.66	2.66
N ₄	3.41	3.41
N ₅	3.75	3.75
N ₁₂	2.83	2.83
N ₁₃	2.81	2.81
N ₁₄	2.89	2.89
N ₁₅	2.58	2.58
N ₂₃	3.74	3.74
N ₂₄	3.04	3.04
N ₂₅	2.86	2.86
N ₃₄	2.75	2.75
N ₃₅	3.45	3.45
N ₄₅	3.49	3.49
C ₁	4.45	4.05
C ₂	3.27	3.61
C ₃	4.68	4.25
C ₄	2.45	2.72
C ₅	2.92	3.33
C ₁₂	3.16	3.51
C ₁₃	2.66	3.07
C ₁₄	2.56	2.95
C ₁₅	4.64	4.26
C ₂₃	3.57	3.22
C ₂₄	3.65	3.28
C ₂₅	3.91	3.55
C ₃₄	3.38	3.01
C ₃₅	4.03	3.64
C ₄₅	3.80	3.52

4.4 COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND PREDICTED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

The comparison of the compressive strength obtained from experiment and that predicted from the model is shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9: Comparison of Experimental and Predicted compressive strength results

Observation points	Experimental compressive strength (Y_E)	Model predicted compressive strength (Y_M)	Difference $D_i = Y_E - Y_M$	% Difference = $\left \frac{Y_E - Y_M}{Y_E} \times 100 \right $
C ₁	4.45	4.05	0.40	8.99
C ₂	3.27	3.61	-0.34	10.40
C ₃	4.68	4.25	0.43	9.19
C ₄	2.45	2.72	-0.27	11.02
C ₅	2.92	3.33	-0.41	14.04
C ₁₂	3.16	3.51	-0.35	11.08
C ₁₃	2.66	3.07	-0.41	15.41
C ₁₄	2.56	2.95	-0.39	15.23
C ₁₅	4.64	4.26	0.38	8.19
C ₂₃	3.57	3.22	0.35	9.80
C ₂₄	3.65	3.28	0.37	10.14
C ₂₅	3.91	3.55	0.36	9.21
C ₃₄	3.38	3.01	0.37	10.95
C ₃₅	4.03	3.64	0.39	9.68
C ₄₅	3.80	3.52	0.28	7.37

4.5 DETERMINATION OF ERROR OF REPLICATES

Error of replicates of the experimental results obtained from the compressive strength test on the sandcrete blocks for both trial and control mixes is computed in Tables 4.10a and 4.10b.

Table 4.10a: Results for error of replicates for trial mixes

Observation points N	Replicate values y_i	\bar{y}	y_i^2	Σy_i	Σy_i^2	$(\Sigma y_i)^2$	Σd^2	S_i^2
1	1.96	1.86	3.84	5.59	10.47	31.25	0.053	0.0265
	1.67		2.79					
	1.96		3.84					
2	3.24	3.09	10.50	9.28	28.74	86.12	0.033	0.0165
	3.02		9.12					
	3.02		9.12					
3	2.74	2.66	7.51	7.97	21.19	63.52	0.0167	0.00835
	2.67		7.13					
	2.56		6.55					
4	3.27	3.41	10.69	10.24	34.99	104.86	0.0367	0.01835
	3.41		11.63					
	3.56		12.67					
5	3.56	3.75	12.67	11.24	42.17	126.34	0.0567	0.02835
	3.84		14.75					
	3.84		14.75					
12	2.99	2.83	8.94	8.5	24.15	72.25	0.067	0.0335
	2.63		6.92					
	2.88		8.29					
13	2.74	2.81	7.51	8.43	23.72	71.06	0.033	0.0165
	2.74		7.51					
	2.95		8.70					
14	2.74	2.89	7.51	8.68	25.16	75.34	0.0467	0.02335
	2.92		8.53					

	3.02		9.12					
15	2.63	2.58	6.92	7.75	20.07	60.06	0.05	0.025
	2.42		5.86					
	2.70		7.29					
23	3.88	3.74	15.05	11.21	41.93	125.66	0.043	0.0215
	3.56		12.67					
	3.77		14.21					
24	2.95	3.04	8.70	9.13	27.8	83.36	0.013	0.0065
	3.09		9.55					
	3.09		9.55					
25	2.88	2.86	8.29	8.57	24.49	73.44	0.01	0.005
	2.77		7.67					
	2.92		8.53					
34	2.67	2.75	7.13	8.26	22.83	68.23	0.087	0.0435
	2.60		6.76					
	2.99		8.94					
35	3.27	3.45	10.69	10.34	35.69	106.92	0.05	0.025
	3.48		12.11					
	3.59		12.89					
45	3.63	3.49	13.18	10.46	36.53	109.41	0.06	0.03
	3.31		10.96					
	3.52		12.39					

$$\sum s_i^2 = s_y^2 = 0.3279$$

$$s_y = \sqrt{s_y^2} = 0.573$$

Table 4.10b: Results for error of replicates for control mixes

Observation points C	Replicate values y_i	\bar{y}	y_i^2	Σy_i	Σy_i^2	$(\Sigma y_i)^2$	Σd^2	S_i^2
1	4.55	4.45	20.70	13.36	59.67	178.49	0.173	0.0865
	4.69		22.00					
	4.12		16.97					
2	3.41	3.27	11.63	9.81	32.11	96.24	0.03	0.015
	3.20		10.24					
	3.20		10.24					
3	4.87	4.68	23.72	14.04	65.8	197.12	0.093	0.0465
	4.44		19.71					
	4.73		22.37					
4	2.67	2.45	7.13	7.36	18.15	54.17	0.093	0.0465
	2.24		5.02					
	2.45		6.00					
5	2.81	2.92	7.90	8.75	25.55	76.56	0.03	0.015
	2.92		8.53					
	3.02		9.12					
12	3.09	3.16	9.55	9.49	30.06	90.06	0.04	0.02
	3.31		10.96					
	3.09		9.55					
13	2.56	2.66	6.55	7.97	21.19	63.52	0.0167	0.00835
	2.74		7.51					
	2.67		7.13					
14	2.70	2.56	7.29	7.68	19.71	58.98	0.05	0.025
	2.60		6.76					
	2.38		5.66					

15	4.59 4.52 4.80	4.64	21.07 20.43 23.04	13.91	64.54	193.49	0.043	0.0215
23	3.59 3.52 3.59	3.57	12.89 12.39 12.89	10.7	38.17	114.49	0.0067	0.00335
24	3.59 3.66 3.70	3.65	12.89 13.40 13.69	10.95	39.98	119.90	0.0133	0.00665
25	4.05 3.77 3.91	3.91	16.40 14.21 15.29	11.73	45.9	137.59	0.037	0.0185
34	3.27 3.38 3.48	3.38	10.69 11.42 12.11	10.13	34.22	102.62	0.0133	0.00665
35	3.91 4.02 4.16	4.03	15.29 16.16 17.31	12.09	48.76	146.17	0.037	0.0185
45	3.91 3.77 3.73	3.80	15.29 14.21 13.91	11.41	43.41	130.19	0.0133	0.00665

$$\sum S_i^2 = S_y^2 = 0.34465$$

$$S_y = \sqrt{S_y^2} = 0.587$$

4.6 TEST FOR ADEQUACY OF SCHEFFE’S RESPONSE MODEL

The test for adequacy of Scheffe’s response model was done using statistical Student t-Test at 95% confidence level and the computations/results are shown in Table 4.11.

Null hypothesis H_0 : This states that there is no significant difference between the experimental and theoretical (model) results.

Alternative hypothesis H_a : This states that there is a significant difference between the experimental and theoretical (model) results.

Table 4.11: Statistical t-Test computations for Scheffe’s response model

Observation points	Experimental compressive strength (YE)	Model predicted compressive strength (YM)	Difference $Di = YE - YM$	$DA - Di$	$(DA - Di)^2$
C_1	4.45	4.05	0.40	-0.3227	0.104135
C_2	3.27	3.61	-0.34	0.4173	0.174139
C_3	4.68	4.25	0.43	-0.3527	0.124397
C_4	2.45	2.72	-0.27	0.3473	0.120617
C_5	2.92	3.33	-0.41	0.4873	0.237461
C_{12}	3.16	3.51	-0.35	0.4273	0.182585
C_{13}	2.66	3.07	-0.41	0.4873	0.237461
C_{14}	2.56	2.95	-0.39	0.4673	0.218369
C_{15}	4.64	4.26	0.38	-0.3027	0.091627
C_{23}	3.57	3.22	0.35	-0.2727	0.074365
C_{24}	3.65	3.28	0.37	-0.2927	0.085673

C ₂₅	3.91	3.55	0.36	-0.2827	0.079919
C ₃₄	3.38	3.01	0.37	-0.2927	0.085673
C ₃₅	4.03	3.64	0.39	-0.3127	0.097781
C ₄₅	3.80	3.52	0.28	-0.2027	0.041087
			∑ = 1.16		∑=1.955289

$$\sum Di = 1.16$$

$$DA = \frac{\sum Di}{N} = \frac{1.16}{15} = 0.0773$$

$$\sum (DA - Di)^2 = 1.955289$$

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum (DA - Di)^2}{(N - 1)} = \frac{1.955289}{14} = 0.1396635$$

$$S = \sqrt{S^2} = \sqrt{0.1396635} = 0.373716$$

$$t = \frac{DA \times N^{0.5}}{S} = \frac{0.0773 \times 15^{0.5}}{0.373716} = 0.801094$$

Degree of freedom = N - 1

$$= 15 - 1 = 14$$

Using 95% confidence level (i.e. 0.05 significance level), and for a two-tail test (as in this research work), divide the significance level by two and subtract the result from 100%.

Therefore, 5% ÷ 2 = 2.5%

Thus, 95% confidence level will be taken to be (100% - 2.5%) = 97.5%

Allowable t using $t_{(97.5\%, 14)} = 2.145$ (obtained from the statistical t-table in Appendix I)

This value is greater than the calculated t. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the experimental values and those obtained from the model. Hence, the model is adequate under statistical t-Test and the null hypothesis is accepted while the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

4.7 EXECUTED COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR DETERMINATION OF OPTIMUM COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

A computer program was written using Visual Basic 6.0 to determine the optimum compressive strength of Fly ash-PSA sandcrete and the mix ratio corresponding to this value. A sample of the executed computer program is presented below:

PROGRAM

Click start

Click okay to continue

What do you want to do??? To calculate mix ratio given desired compressive strength or calculate compressive strength given desired mix ratio? Type 1 or 0 and click okay

Type 1 and click okay

What is the desired compressive strength???

Enter value and click okay

OUTPUT

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.576, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.014, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.89

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.576, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.014, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.89

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.576, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.014, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.89

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.576, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.014, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.89

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.576, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.014, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.89

Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.572, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.011, SAND = 5.81

Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.572, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.011, SAND = 5.81

Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.572, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.011, SAND = 5.81

Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.572, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.011, SAND = 5.81

Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.572, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.011, SAND = 5.81

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.57, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.75

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.57, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.75

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.57, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.75

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.57, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.75

Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.57, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.75
Y = 2.2, WATER = 0.569, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.73
Y = 2.2, WATER = 0.569, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.73
Y = 2.2, WATER = 0.569, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.73
Y = 2.2, WATER = 0.569, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.73
Y = 2.2, WATER = 0.569, CEMENT = 0.975, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.73
Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.568, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.71
Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.568, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.71
Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.568, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.71
Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.568, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.71
Y = 2.21, WATER = 0.568, CEMENT = 0.974, PSA = 0.013, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.71
Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.562, CEMENT = 0.973, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.54
Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.562, CEMENT = 0.973, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.54
Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.562, CEMENT = 0.973, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.54
Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.562, CEMENT = 0.973, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.54
Y = 2.19, WATER = 0.562, CEMENT = 0.973, PSA = 0.015, FLY ASH = 0.012, SAND = 5.54

OPTIMUM COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH PREDICTABLE BY THIS MODEL IS

3.9175 N/mm²

THE CORRESPONDING MIXTURE RATIO IS AS FOLLOWS:

WATER = 0.675, CEMENT = 1.19, PSA = 0.0375, FLY ASH = 0.0225, SAND = 6.25

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn in completion of this research work:

- i. Both fly ash and PSA were characterized to have good cementitious properties/compositions.
- ii. The experimental compressive strength of the cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks were determined by carrying out compressive strength test on the samples.
- iii. A mathematical model was formulated for prediction of compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks.
- iv. Appropriate comparison of the experimental compressive strength and model-predicted compressive strength was made and the maximum percentage difference between both was found to be 15.41%.
- v. The model developed was tested using statistical Student t-Test at 5% significance level, and was found to be adequate.
- vi. Scheffe's simplex model was used to develop a computer program. The computer program developed using Visual Basic 6.0 can predict all possible combinations of mix proportions of fly ash-PSA sandcrete blocks given the compressive strength, and vice versa.
- vii. The optimum compressive strength as predicted by the model was 3.9175 N/mm^2 . The corresponding mix ratio for the optimum compressive strength is:
Water = 0.675, Cement = 1.19, PSA = 0.0375, Fly ash = 0.0225, Sand = 6.25.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the results obtained in this research work:

- i. Since the model passed the adequacy test, it should be used to determine the compressive strength of cement blended Fly ash-PSA sandcrete given any mix ratio, and vice versa.
- ii. More research work should be done using Scheffe's simplex theory/lattice to predict the compressive strength of sandcrete with more than five components.
- iii. More research work should be carried out on the use of Scheffe's simplex theory/lattice for the determination and prediction of other properties of sandcrete.

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APPENDIX I

Statistical t-table

The Cumulative Distribution Function for the t-Distribution

df	90%	95%	97.5%	99%	99.5%	99.9%
1	3.078	6.314	12.706	31.821	63.657	318.309
2	1.886	2.920	4.303	6.965	9.925	22.327
3	1.638	2.353	3.183	4.541	5.841	10.215
4	1.533	2.132	2.777	3.747	4.604	7.173
5	1.476	2.015	2.571	3.365	4.032	5.893
6	1.440	1.943	2.447	3.143	3.708	5.208
7	1.415	1.895	2.365	2.998	3.500	4.785
8	1.397	1.860	2.306	2.897	3.355	4.501
9	1.383	1.833	2.262	2.822	3.250	4.297
10	1.372	1.812	2.228	2.764	3.169	4.144
11	1.363	1.796	2.201	2.718	3.106	4.025
12	1.356	1.782	2.179	2.681	3.055	3.930
13	1.350	1.771	2.160	2.650	3.012	3.852
14	1.345	1.761	2.145	2.625	2.977	3.787
15	1.341	1.753	2.132	2.603	2.947	3.733
16	1.337	1.746	2.120	2.584	2.921	3.686
17	1.333	1.740	2.110	2.567	2.898	3.646
18	1.330	1.734	2.101	2.552	2.879	3.611
19	1.328	1.729	2.093	2.540	2.861	3.580
20	1.325	1.725	2.086	2.528	2.845	3.552
21	1.323	1.721	2.080	2.518	2.831	3.527
22	1.321	1.717	2.074	2.508	2.819	3.505
23	1.319	1.714	2.069	2.500	2.807	3.485
24	1.318	1.711	2.064	2.492	2.797	3.467
25	1.316	1.708	2.060	2.485	2.788	3.450
26	1.315	1.706	2.056	2.479	2.779	3.435
27	1.314	1.703	2.052	2.473	2.771	3.421
28	1.313	1.701	2.048	2.467	2.763	3.408
29	1.311	1.699	2.045	2.462	2.756	3.396
30	1.310	1.697	2.042	2.457	2.750	3.385
40	1.303	1.684	2.021	2.423	2.705	3.307
50	1.299	1.676	2.009	2.403	2.678	3.262
60	1.296	1.671	2.000	2.390	2.660	3.232
80	1.292	1.664	1.990	2.374	2.639	3.195
100	1.290	1.660	1.984	2.364	2.626	3.174
200	1.286	1.653	1.972	2.345	2.601	3.132
∞	1.282	1.645	1.960	2.326	2.576	3.090

APPENDIX II

COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR PREDICTION OF CEMENT BLENDED FLY ASH-PSA SANDCRETE

```
Private Sub ENDMNU_Click()
```

```
End
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub STARTMNU_Click()
```

```
Rem ONE COMPONENT
```

```
Cls: Text1.Text = " "
```

```
ReDim x(4)
```

```
'SCHEFFE'S SIMPLEX MODEL
```

```
Print " THE PROGRAM WAS WRITTEN BY"
```

```
Print: Print
```

```
Print " Nwagwu Chimaobi Onyedikachi 20121797373"
```

```
Print:
```

```
WWWWW = InputBox("CLICK OK. TO CONTINUE"): Cls
```

```
Print: Print " THIS PROJECT IS IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE AWARD"
```

```
Print " OF B. ENG IN CIVIL ENGINEERING"
```

```
WWWWW = InputBox("CLICK OK. TO CONTINUE"): Cls
```

```
Print " WE ACKNOWLEDGE OUR SUPERVISOR, Engr. Lewechi Anyaogu"
```

```
Print " FOR INITIATING AND SUPERVISING THIS PROJECT"
```

```
WWWWW = InputBox("CLICK OK. TO CONTINUE"): Cls
```

```
'CIVIL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT, FUTO
```

CT = 0: OPSTRENGTH = 0

ReDim x(15), A(5, 5), z(5), N(15), B(5, 5), ZZ(5): QQ = 1

ReDim U(2000, 5), WW(2000)

v = 1

Cls

N1 = 1.86: N2 = 3.09: N3 = 2.66: N4 = 3.41: N5 = 3.75

N6 = 2.83: N7 = 2.81: N8 = 2.89: N9 = 2.58: N10 = 3.74

N11 = 3.04: N12 = 2.86: N13 = 2.75: N14 = 3.45: N15 = 3.49

5 QQ = InputBox("WHAT DO YOU WANT TO DO? TO CALCULATE MIX RATIOS GIVEN DESIRED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OR CALCULATING COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH GIVEN MIX RATIO?", "IF THE STRENGTH IS KNOWN TYPE 1 ELSE TYPE 0", "TYPE 1 OR 0 and CLICK OK")

If QQ <> 1 And QQ <> 0 Then EE = InputBox("No Way! You must ENTER 1 or 0", , "CLICK OK and do so"): GoTo 5

If QQ = 0 Then GoTo 900

Rem *** CONVERSION MATRIX ***

A(1, 1) = 0.58: A(1, 2) = 0.56: A(1, 3) = 0.54: A(1, 4) = 0.52: A(1, 5) = 0.5

A(2, 1) = 0.98: A(2, 2) = 0.96: A(2, 3) = 0.92: A(2, 4) = 0.95: A(2, 5) = 0.95

A(3, 1) = 0.01: A(3, 2) = 0.02: A(3, 3) = 0.05: A(3, 4) = 0.04: A(3, 5) = 0.03

A(4, 1) = 0.01: A(4, 2) = 0.02: A(4, 3) = 0.03: A(4, 4) = 0.01: A(4, 5) = 0.02

A(5, 1) = 6: A(5, 2) = 5.5: A(5, 3) = 5: A(5, 4) = 4.5: A(5, 5) = 4

YY = InputBox("WHAT IS THE DESIRED Compressive STRENGTH?"): YY = YY * 1

Rem ONE COMPONENT

Q = -5: R = 1: E = 1

50 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

x(E) = 1

If Q = 0 Then GoTo 60

GoTo 2000

55 E = E + 1: Q = Q + 1: GoTo 50

60 Rem TWO COMPONENTS

R = R + 1: F = 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1: K1 = 0.9: K2 = 0.1: v = 6

65 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

x(F) = K1: x(E) = K2

If T = 6 Then GoTo 70

If J = v Then GoTo 80

If W = 5 Then GoTo 90

GoTo 2000

67 T = T + 1: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K2 = K2 + 0.1: GoTo 65

70 J = J + 1: E = E + 1: K1 = 0.9: K2 = 0.1: T = 1: GoTo 65

80 J = 1: v = v - 1: F = F + 1: E = F + 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: K1 = 0.9: K2 = 0.1: GoTo 65

90 Rem THREE COMPONENTS

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1

K1 = 0.89: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.1

100 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

If E = 5 Then x(2) = K3: x(1) = K1: x(E) = 0.01: GoTo 110

x(1) = K1: x(E) = 0.01: x(E + 1) = K3

110 If T = 99 Then GoTo 120

If J = 5 Then GoTo 130
 If W = 10 Then GoTo 140
 GoTo 2000
 115 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 110
 120 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 100
 130 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K3 = K3 + 0.1: GoTo 100
 140 Rem THREE COMPONENTS CONTINUED
 R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1
 K1 = 0.69: K2 = 0.11: K3 = 0.2
 150 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I
 If E = 5 Then x(2) = K3: x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: GoTo 160
 x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3
 160 If T = 99 Then GoTo 170
 If J = 5 Then GoTo 180
 If W = 8 Then GoTo 190
 GoTo 2000
 165 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 160
 170 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 150
 180 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K3 = K3 + 0.1: GoTo 150
 190 Rem FOUR COMPONENTS
 R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1
 K1 = 0.79: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.1: K4 = 0.1
 200 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

If E = 4 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K4: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: GoTo 210

If E = 5 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K3: x(3) = K4: x(E) = K2: GoTo 210

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: x(E + 2) = K4

210 If T = 99 Then GoTo 220

If J = 5 Then GoTo 230

If W = 9 Then GoTo 240

GoTo 2000

215 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 210

220 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 200

230 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K4 = K4 + 0.1: GoTo 200

240 Rem FOUR COMPONENTS CONTINUED

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1

K1 = 0.59: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.2: K4 = 0.2

250 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

If E = 4 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K4: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: GoTo 260

If E = 5 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K3: x(3) = K4: x(E) = K2: GoTo 260

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: x(E + 2) = K4

260 If T = 99 Then GoTo 270

If J = 5 Then GoTo 280

If W = 7 Then GoTo 290

GoTo 2000

265 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 260

270 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 250

280 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K4 = K4 + 0.1: GoTo 250

290 Rem FOUR COMPONENTS CONTINUED AGAIN

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1

K1 = 0.29: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.4: K4 = 0.3

300 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I

If E = 4 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K4: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: GoTo 310

If E = 5 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K3: x(3) = K4: x(E) = K2: GoTo 310

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3: x(E + 2) = K4

310 If T = 99 Then GoTo 320

If J = 5 Then GoTo 330

If W = 4 Then GoTo 340

GoTo 2000

315 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 310

320 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 300

330 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K4 = K4 + 0.1: GoTo 300

340 Rem FOUR COMPONENTS CONTINUED AGAIN AGAIN

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1

350 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0.25: Next I

x(E) = 0

360 If T = 6 Then GoTo 370

GoTo 2000

365 T = T + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 350

370 Rem FIVE COMPONENTS

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1

K1 = 0.69: K2 = 0.01: K5 = 0.1

380 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0.1: Next I

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(5) = K5

390 If T = 99 Then GoTo 400

If J = 5 Then GoTo 410

If W = 8 Then GoTo 420

GoTo 2000

395 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 390

400 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 380

410 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K5 = K5 + 0.1: GoTo 380

420 Rem FIVE COMPONENTS CONTINUED

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1: W = 1

K1 = 0.49: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.1: K4 = 0.2: K5 = 0.2

430 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0.1: Next I

If E = 2 Then x(E + 1) = K3: x(E + 2) = K4: x(E + 3) = K5: GoTo 440

If E = 3 Then x(E + 1) = K3: x(E + 2) = K4: x(2) = K5: GoTo 440

If E = 4 Then x(E + 1) = K3: x(2) = K4: x(3) = K5: GoTo 440

If E = 5 Then x(2) = K3: x(3) = K4: x(4) = K5

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(5) = K5

440 x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2

450 If T = 99 Then GoTo 460

If J = 5 Then GoTo 470

If W = 6 Then GoTo 480

GoTo 2000

455 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 450

460 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 430

470 J = 1: T = 1: W = W + 1: E = 2: K1 = K1 - 0.1: K5 = K5 + 0.1: GoTo 430

480 Rem FIVE COMPONENTS CONTINUED AGAIN

R = R + 1: E = 2: T = 1: J = 1

K1 = 0.29: K2 = 0.01: K3 = 0.1: K4 = 0.3: K5 = 0.3

490 For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0.3: Next I

If E = 5 Then x(1) = K1: x(2) = K3: x(E) = K2: GoTo 500

x(1) = K1: x(E) = K2: x(E + 1) = K3

500 If T = 99 Then GoTo 510

If J = 5 Then GoTo 520

GoTo 2000

515 T = T + 1: x(1) = x(1) - 0.01: x(E) = x(E) + 0.01: GoTo 500

510 T = 1: J = J + 1: E = E + 1: GoTo 490

520 Rem FIVE COMPONENTS CONTINUED AGAIN AGAIN

R = R + 1

x(1) = 0.2: x(2) = 0.2: x(3) = 0.2: x(4) = 0.2: x(5) = 0.2

GoTo 2000

525 Rem END OF THE COMBINATIONS

GoTo 2100

2000 Rem PRINTING OF RESULTS

For I = 1 To 5: z(I) = 0: Next I

For I = 1 To 5: For JJ = 1 To 5: z(I) = z(I) + A(I, JJ) * x(JJ): Next JJ: Next I

If z(1) < 0 Or z(2) < 0 Or z(3) < 0 Or z(4) < 0 Or z(5) < 0 Then GoTo 830

If z(1) < 0.49 Then GoTo 830

'If Z(2) <> 1 Then GoTo 830

If x(1) < 0 Or x(2) < 0 Or x(3) < 0 Or x(4) < 0 Or x(5) < 0 Then GoTo 830

If x(1) > 1 Or x(2) > 1 Or x(3) > 1 Or x(4) > 1 Or x(5) > 1 Then GoTo 830

Y = x(1) * (1 - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N1 + x(2) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N2 + x(3) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N3

Y = Y + x(4) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(5)) * N4 + x(5) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4)) * N5 + 4 * N6 * x(1) * x(2) + 4 * N7 * x(1) * x(3)

Y = Y + 4 * N8 * x(1) * x(4) + 4 * N9 * x(1) * x(5) + 4 * N10 * x(2) * x(3) + 4 * N11 * x(2) * x(4) + 4 * N12 * x(2) * x(5) + 4 * N13 * x(3) * x(4) + 4 * N14 * x(3) * x(5) + 4 * N15 * x(4) * x(5)

If Y > OPSTRENGTH Then For I = 1 To 5: ZZ(I) = 0: Next I

If Y > OPSTRENGTH Then OPSTRENGTH = Y: For I = 1 To 5: For JJ = 1 To 5: ZZ(I) = ZZ(I) + A(I, JJ) * x(JJ): Next JJ: Next I

If Y > YY - 0.01 And Y < YY + 0.01 Then GoTo 810 Else GoTo 830

810 CT = CT + 1

For I = 1 To 5: z(I) = 0: Next I

For I = 1 To 5

For JJ = 1 To 5

z(I) = z(I) + A(I, JJ) * x(JJ)

Next JJ

Next I

820 $U(v, 1) = z(1): U(v, 2) = z(2): U(v, 3) = z(3): U(v, 4) = z(4): U(v, 5) = z(5)$

$WW(v) = Y$

$v = v + 1$

830

If R = 1 Then GoTo 55

If R = 2 Then GoTo 67

If R = 3 Then GoTo 115

If R = 4 Then GoTo 165

If R = 5 Then GoTo 215

If R = 6 Then GoTo 265

If R = 7 Then GoTo 315

If R = 8 Then GoTo 365

If R = 9 Then GoTo 395

If R = 10 Then GoTo 455

If R = 11 Then GoTo 515

If R = 12 Then GoTo 525

2100

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("Y" & vbTab & "water" & vbTab & "Cement" & vbTab & "PSA" & vbTab & "Fly Ash" & vbTab & "Sand") & vbCrLf

For I = 1 To v

For J = 1 To 5

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(WW(I), "0.0#")) & vbTab

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(U(I, 1), "0.00#")) & vbTab

```

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(U(I, 2), "0.00#")) & vbTab
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(U(I, 3), "0.00#")) & vbTab
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(U(I, 4), "0.00#")) & vbTab
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(Format(U(I, 5), "0.00#")) & vbCrLf
Next J
Next I
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + (" ") & vbCrLf: Text1.Text = Text1.Text + (" ") & vbCrLf
If CT = 0 Then Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("***  SORRY THE COMPRESSIVE
STRENGTH IS OUTSIDE THE FACTOR SPACE  ***") & vbCrLf
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("OPTIMUM COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH PREDICTABLE
BY THIS MODEL IS ") & vbCrLf
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(OPSTRENGTH) & vbCrLf
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" THE CORRESPONDING MIXTURE RATIO IS AS
FOLLOWS:") & vbCrLf
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("  WATER =" & vbTab & vbTab & ZZ(1) & vbTab & vbTab
& "  CEMENT =" & vbTab & ZZ(2)) & vbTab
Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("  PSA =" & vbTab & vbTab & ZZ(3) & vbTab & vbTab & "
Fly Ash =" & vbTab & ZZ(4) & "  Sand =" & vbTab & ZZ(5)) & vbCrLf
GoTo 22222
900
Cls
Y = 0
For I = 1 To 5: x(I) = 0: Next I
Rem *** RESPONSE AT THE CHOSEN 15 POINTS ON THE FACTOR SPACE FOR THE
MODEL ***

```

N1 = 1.86: N2 = 3.09: N3 = 2.66: N4 = 3.41: N5 = 3.75

N6 = 2.83: N7 = 2.81: N8 = 2.89: N9 = 2.58: N10 = 3.74

N11 = 3.04: N12 = 2.86: N13 = 2.75: N14 = 3.45: N15 = 3.49

3010 Rem *** CONVERSION MATRIX ****

B(1, 1) = -2500: B(1, 2) = 850: B(1, 3) = 850: B(1, 4) = 850: B(1, 5) = 100

B(2, 1) = 3762.5: B(2, 2) = -1280.5: B(2, 3) = -1305.5: B(2, 4) = -1280.5: B(2, 5) = -150

B(3, 1) = -1245.833333: B(3, 2) = 421.5: B(3, 3) = 446.5: B(3, 4) = 454.8333333: B(3, 5) = 50

B(4, 1) = 1254.166667: B(4, 2) = -426.5: B(4, 3) = -401.5: B(4, 4) = -493.1666667: B(4, 5) = -50

B(5, 1) = -1270.833333: B(5, 2) = 436.5: B(5, 3) = 411.5: B(5, 4) = 469.8333333: B(5, 5) = 50

Rem *** ACTUAL MIXTURE COMPONENTS ****

z(1) = InputBox("ENTER THE VALUE OF Water")

z(2) = InputBox("ENTER THE VALUE OF Cement")

z(3) = InputBox("ENTER THE VALUE OF PSA")

z(4) = InputBox("ENTER THE VALUE OF Fly Ash")

z(5) = InputBox("ENTER THE VALUE OF Sand")

Rem *** PSEUDO MIXTURE COMPONENTS ***

For I = 1 To 5

For JJ = 1 To 5

x(I) = x(I) + B(I, JJ) * z(JJ)

Next JJ

Next I

Rem *** CALCULATING THE STRENGTH (RESPONSE) ****

$Y = x(1) * (1 - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N1 + x(2) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N2 + x(3) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(4) - 2 * x(5)) * N3$

$Y = Y + x(4) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(5)) * N4 + x(5) * (1 - 2 * x(1) - 2 * x(2) - 2 * x(3) - 2 * x(4)) * N5 + 4 * N6 * x(1) * x(2) + 4 * N7 * x(1) * x(3)$

$Y = Y + 4 * N8 * x(1) * x(4) + 4 * N9 * x(1) * x(5) + 4 * N10 * x(2) * x(3) + 4 * N11 * x(2) * x(4) + 4 * N12 * x(2) * x(5) + 4 * N13 * x(3) * x(4) + 4 * N14 * x(3) * x(5) + 4 * N15 * x(4) * x(5)$

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr("Y =" & vbTab & Format(Y, "0.00#") & ",") & vbTab

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" WATER =" & vbTab & Format(z(1), "0.00#") & ",") & vbTab

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" CEMENT =" & vbTab & Format(z(2), "0.00#") & ",") & vbTab

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" PSA =" & vbTab & Format(z(3), "0.00#") & ",") & vbTab

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" Fly Ash =" & vbTab & Format(z(4), "0.00#") & ",") & vbCrLf

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + CStr(" Sand =" & vbTab & Format(z(5), "0.00#") & ",") & vbCrLf

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + (" ") & vbCrLf: Text1.Text = Text1.Text + (" ") & vbCrLf

For I = 1 To 5

'Print Format(X(I), "0.00#"),

Text1.Text = Text1.Text + (Format(x(I), "0.00#") & vbTab)

Next I

22222

End Sub